

Update of the definition of vegetative filter strip scenarios for Europe

Report number
120333-1

Project number
120333

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Date
March 19, 2025

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Project number: 120333
Report number: 120333-1

Substance: n.a.

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Report completion date: March 19, 2025

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Environmental risk assessment procedures for pesticides in the context of approval and authorization at EU and national level must keep up with scientific developments and therefore have to be updated regularly.

The standardised FOCUS surface water approach for the estimation of predicted environmental concentrations of pesticides in surface water and sediment consists of a total of four tiers (Steps 1 to 4). Mitigation measures for spray drift and surface runoff can be included in Step 4. While spray drift inputs are typically mitigated with drift-reducing nozzles and no-spray zones, the most widely implemented mitigation measure to reduce the input of pesticides to surface waters via surface runoff and erosion are vegetative filter strips (VFS).

The SWAN tool for higher-tier surface water exposure assessment implements fixed runoff and erosion reduction efficiencies according to the report of the FOCUS Landscape and Mitigation Working Group. Since SWAN version 3 the tool also includes the option to apply mitigation using the model VFSSMOD, a numerical, mechanistic, dynamic and event-based model for predicting runoff reduction, sediment deposition, and pesticide trapping across a vegetative filter strip (VFS). VFSSMOD was applied by Brown et al. (2012) to develop realistic worst case VFS scenarios for calculating the reduction of pesticide input to surface water for the four FOCUS runoff scenarios. The resulting scenarios were subsequently included in SWAN.

Since then, with the publication of substantial scientific developments, VFSSMOD has been improved in its underlying assumptions and process descriptions. This requires also updating the original VFS scenarios of Brown et al. (2012) using the new VFSSMOD version. Moreover, new EU soil profile and land cover data have become available, and the United Kingdom has left the EU. Hence, the population of the spatial cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) of the relative reduction of incoming pesticide load (ΔP) by VFS needed to be updated. The objective of this study was therefore to update and improve the SWAN-VFSSMOD scenarios for EU pesticide risk assessment.

In this study, 64 new spatial CDFs of ΔP have been created. Out of these, the four CDFs corresponding to the most relevant combination of input factors in the context of FOCUS were selected for the new SWAN-VFSSMOD scenarios. From those, the soil profiles corresponding to the 10th percentile of ΔP (thus, the 90th percentile worst case in space) were selected for parameterization of VFSSMOD in SWAN 5.2.

A comparison of the new spatial CDFs with predicted trapping efficiencies ΔP obtained with the previous SWAN-VFSSMOD scenarios and the old VFSSMOD version yielded that the new SWAN-VFSSMOD scenarios are overall more conservative than the old ones. Analysis of the new CDFs with regard to soil texture confirmed that the approach of selecting overall 90th percentile worst case soil profiles for the VFS scenarios is reasonable. As expected, some texture classes have higher vulnerability than others. The general ranking of texture classes with respect to ΔP (Coarse > Medium > Fine > Medium Fine > Very Fine) reflects the soil hydraulic properties; notably the predicted saturated conductivity is on average lowest for soils with texture classes Medium Fine (very high silt content) and Very Fine (very high clay content).

In conclusion, this study has derived a set of updated VFSSMOD scenarios for FOCUS Step 4 simulations. The new 90th percentile worst case profiles for SWAN-VFSSMOD correspond to the state of the art of VFS scientific knowledge and the most recent available soil profile databases and land cover data. The updated SWAN-VFSSMOD scenarios are both more realistic and more protective than the old ones. While the derived SWAN-VFSSMOD scenarios represent the best estimate of a 90th percentile worst case given the available data, this report may also offer a blueprint for revising the scenarios as new data become available. Potential future updates of the SWAN-VFSSMOD scenarios should include first a revision of the FOCUS scenario maps because of climate change.

GLOSSARY

Term	Definition
ΔE	relative reduction of incoming eroded sediment load by the Vegetative Filter Strip (VFS)
ΔP	relative reduction of incoming pesticide load by the VFS
ΔQ	relative reduction of total inflow (runoff + rainfall) by the VFS
ΔR	relative reduction of incoming surface runoff by the VFS
CDF	Cumulative Distribution Function
CLC	CORINE Land Cover
CORINE	Coordination of Information on the Environment
CRU	Climatic Research Unit
DegT ₅₀	Degradation time: Time taken for 50 % of the substance to disappear from a compartment by degradation processes
DegT ₉₀	Degradation time: Time taken for 90 % of the substance to disappear from a compartment by degradation processes
FC	Field capacity water content (VFSSMOD parameter)
FOCUS	FORum for the Coordination of pesticide fate models and their USE
HYPRES	HYdraulic PRoperties of European Soils
K_d	linear adsorption coefficient; ratio of concentration in the sorbed and the liquid phase
K_{foc}	Adsorption/desorption coefficient normalised for organic carbon content in soil following a Freundlich adsorption isotherm
K_{oc}	Linear adsorption coefficient normalised to soil organic carbon content
K_{om}	Linear adsorption coefficient normalised to soil organic matter content
K_{ow}	n-Octanol/ water partitioning coefficient
MARS	Monitoring Agricultural Resources
MUSLE	Modified Universal Soil Loss Equation
MUSS	Modified version of MUSLE for small catchments; meaning of acronym unknown
NUTS	Nomenclature des Unités Territoriales Statistiques (Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics)
OS	saturated water content (VFSSMOD parameter)
ptf	pedotransfer function
PEC _{sed}	Predicted environmental concentration in sediment
PEC _{sw}	Predicted environmental concentration in surface water
SAV	Green-Ampt average suction at wetting front (VFSSMOD parameter)
SGDBE	Soil Geographical Database of Europe
SMU	Soil Mapping Unit
SPADE	Soil Profile Analytical Database for Europe
STU	Soil Typological Unit
SWAN	Surface Water Assessment eNabler
UH	Unit Hydrograph or Hydrologic Utility
VFS	Vegetative (or Vegetated) Filter Strip
VFSSMOD	Vegetative Filter Strips Modeling System
VKS	vertical saturated conductivity (VFSSMOD parameter)
VL	VFS length in flow direction (VFSSMOD parameter), often referred to as “buffer strip width”

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1 INTRODUCTION

The FOCUS Surface Water Scenarios group developed standardised approaches for the estimation of predicted environmental concentrations of pesticides in surface water and sediment which are needed for the aquatic risk assessment in the frame of the regulatory process within the European Union (FOCUS 2001, 2015). The standardised approach consists of a total of four tiers (Steps 1 to 4). FOCUS Steps 1-3 adopt standardised approaches that account for the input of pesticides into surface water via the entry pathways drift, drainage and runoff/erosion. In Step 4 mitigation measures for spray drift and surface runoff can be simulated. While spray drift inputs are typically mitigated with drift-reducing nozzles and no-spray zones, the most widely implemented mitigation measure to reduce the input of pesticides and other pollutants to surface waters via surface runoff and erosion are vegetative filter strips (VFS). The SWAN tool for Step4 modelling (ECPA, 2018) implements runoff and erosion reduction efficiencies following the report of the FOCUS Landscape and Mitigation Working Group (FOCUS, 2007). Since SWAN version 3 (ECPA, 2012), it also includes the option to apply mitigation using the vegetative filter strip model VFSSMOD. VFSSMOD (Muñoz-Carpena et al., 1999; Muñoz-Carpena and Parsons, 2022) is a numerical, mechanistic, dynamic and event-based model for predicting runoff reduction, sediment deposition and pesticide trapping across a VFS. In Brown et al. (2012) the VFSSMOD model was applied to develop realistic worst case VFS scenarios for calculating the reduction of pesticide input to surface water by VFS for the four FOCUS runoff scenarios.

In summary, Brown et al. (2012) performed, for each FOCUS R scenario, the following VFSSMOD simulations (with VFSSMOD v. 4.2.4):

- Rainfall volume: 30 mm
- Event duration: 1 h / 8 h
- Koc 100 and 10000 L kg⁻¹
- VFS length in flow direction (VL): 10 m
- Rainfall and field runoff hydrographs were produced with the utility UH (Muñoz-Carpena and Parsons, 2022)
- VFSSMOD simulations were run for all soil profiles available in the SPADE2 database (Hannam et al., 2009) for the spatial extent of the respective FOCUS scenario (FOCUS, 2001)

From the spatial cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the target variable (relative reduction of incoming pesticide load, ΔP) the 10th percentile soil profile was extracted, which yielded a 90th percentile worst case set of profile-specific VFSSMOD parameters:

- Vertical saturated conductivity K_s (VFSSMOD parameter VKS)
- Saturated water content Θ_s (VFSSMOD parameter OS)
- Field capacity water content Θ_{fc} (VFSSMOD parameter FC)

The event duration (and thus rainfall intensity) had some influence on the vulnerability ranking of soil profiles (i.e. their position on the CDFs); however, the ranking was identical at the ends of the distributions (Brown et al. 2012). Koc was found to have no influence on the vulnerability ranking. Furthermore, tests performed for different rainfall volumes and VFS lengths yielded only slight effects on the soil vulnerability ranking for the former and hardly any effects for the latter.

The realistic worst case VFS scenarios derived for the four FOCUS R scenarios by Brown et al. (2012) and the VFSSMOD version used by Brown et al. were subsequently included in the SWAN 3 software package (Tessella, 2012).

The latest published version of SWAN (v. 5.01; ECPA, 2018) still uses the same VFSSMOD version (v. 4.2.4) as SWAN 3. However, this version is outdated in several respects. Since the publication of Brown et al. (2012), substantial scientific efforts have been made to further improve VFSSMOD and its underlying assumptions and process descriptions:

- Improved pesticide trapping equations (Reichenberger et al., 2019);
- New method to estimate the highly sensitive parameter “median particle diameter” (d50; Reichenberger et al., 2023). The improved d50 parametrisation method provides more realistic sediment reduction efficiencies than the default value of 20 µm proposed by Brown et al. (2012) that has been used so far in SWAN-VFSMOD;
- Implementation of a new method for calculating the remobilisation of residues and an analytical solution for leaching in the VFS (Muñoz-Carpena et al., in preparation);
- Implementation of a shallow water table option (Muñoz-Carpena et al., 2018; Lauvernet and Muñoz-Carpena, 2018)

Hence, the simulation study of Brown et al. (2012) needed to be redone with the latest VFSMOD version, which integrates the scientific progress mentioned above. Moreover, new soil profile and land cover data have become available in the meantime, and the United Kingdom has left the EU. Hence, the population of the spatial CDFs needed to be updated.

Therefore, the objective of this study is the corresponding update and improvement of the SWAN-VFSMOD scenarios, with the aim to apply these scenarios in the frame of the EU risk assessment.

The requirements for this study were the following:

- Use latest official VFSMOD version (v. 4.5.2)
- Include additional soil profile data which have become available since the publication of Brown et al. (2012), thus improving the spatial coverage of the CDFs
- Use most recent land cover map to update the areas of agricultural land
- Exclude UK from the list of countries to be included in the spatial CDF

The deliverables of this study were:

- Spatial cumulative distribution functions (CDF) of the pesticide reduction efficiency predicted by VFSMOD
- 90th percentile worst-case profiles with VFSMOD parameters for inclusion in SWAN-VFSMOD, i.e. 10th percentile profiles with respect to pesticide trapping
- Technical report (this document)
- Peer-reviewed paper to supersede the report of Brown et al. (2012)

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The work started in October 2022 and followed an iterative process. Only the final VFSMOD runs and cumulative distribution functions will be discussed in detail.

2.1 Update of spatial basis and determination of soil profiles to be simulated

The new extent should comprise the 27 current EU member states and exclude UK. The FOCUS scenario shapefiles to be used (Hollis, 2007) were provided by the clients. These shapefiles were compared with the original FOCUS R scenario shapefiles from FOCUS (2001) and turned out to be identical. All shapefiles had been created in 2000; only the coordinate reference system was changed in 2002 (to Lambert Azimuth Equal Area, origin: 9° E, 48° N). The only difference between the Hollis (2007) shapefiles and Figures 3.4.7-3.4.10 in FOCUS (2001) was found to be that the latter have been clipped with the map of EU member states at that time (EU 15).

The FOCUS scenario shapefiles are based on:

- Soil Geographical Database of Europe SGDBE (Le Bas et al., 1998)
- Climatic Research Unit (CRU) climate grid, 0.5°* 0.5°(Hulme et al., 1995)

The CRU climate grid has a spatial resolution of $0.5^\circ * 0.5^\circ$ degrees and contains long-term monthly averages of precipitation, temperature, wind speed, sunshine hours, cloud cover, vapour pressure, relative humidity and frost days based on the observation period 1961-1990. Since climate has significantly changed since then, an update of the FOCUS scenario shapefiles would be recommended in the future.

The following soil datasets were used as input:

- Tables from SGDBE (Le Bas et al., 1998):
 - stuorg.dbf: relation between Soil Mapping Units (SMU) and Soil Typological Units (STU)
 - stu_sgdbe.dbf: dominant and secondary land use of each STU
- Soil profile databases
 - SPADE2 (Hannam et al., 2009): contains 5575 profiles from 17 countries
 - SPADE14 (Breuning-Madsen et al., 2015): contains 1071 profiles from 28 countries

In the next step we determined the unique profile / scenario combinations to be simulated for the shapefiles of Hollis (2007).

The procedure was as follows:

- 1) Intersect the FOCUS scenario shapefiles with a map of administrative boundaries of EU countries (NUTS0; Eurostat, 2023a, 2023b)
- 2) Aggregate the attribute tables of the obtained four shapefiles, merge them into one table by appending and join stuorg.dbf → R1234_NUTS_agg_leftjoin_stuorg.xlsx. This file contains all combinations of SMU, country, FOCUS_scenario and STU that are needed. It comprises 26 countries (Table 1) and 2560 records.
- 3) Join SPADE14 and SPADE2 to above table → table stuorg-stu_sgdbe-spade14-spade2-R1234.xlsx
- 4) Determine unique combinations of profileID and R scenario
→ 3074 combinations of R scenario and soil profile to be simulated

A more detailed description of steps 3 and 4 is given in section 6.6. The script (import_extended.R) can be found in the digital annex (see section 6.11).

In order to stay as close as possible to the method of Brown et al. (2012), the procedure with an intersection with CORINE Land Cover 2018 (EEA, 2020; Figure 1) was repeated as a 2nd step:

- 1) Intersect the FOCUS scenario shapefiles with a map of administrative boundaries of EU countries (NUTS0; Eurostat, 2023a, 2023b)
- 2) Analogously to Brown et al. (2012), intersect the shapefile resulting from 1) with CORINE Land Cover (CLC) 2018 (EEA, 2020) class 2 (agricultural land)
- 3) Aggregate the attribute tables of the obtained four shapefiles, merge them into one table by appending and join stuorg.dbf → R1234_NUTS_CLC_agg_leftjoin_stuorg.xlsx. This file contains all combinations of SMU, country, CLC subclass, FOCUS_scenario and STU that are needed. It comprises 25 countries (also Turkey) and 13923 records.

Figure 1 CORINE Land Cover 2018 map of Europe. Source: <https://sdi.eea.europa.eu/>

Table 1 List of countries after intersecting the FOCUS scenario shapefiles with the map of administrative boundaries (NUTS0)

NUTS country code	NUTS country name	country name (English)
AL	Shqipëria	Albania
AT	Österreich	Austria
BE	Belgique/België	Belgium
BG	България	Bulgaria

NUTS country code	NUTS country name	country name (English)
CH	Schweiz/Suisse/Svizzera	Switzerland
CZ	Česko	Czech Republic
DE	Deutschland	Germany
EL	Ελλάδα	Greece
ES	España	Spain
FR	France	Francia
HR	Hrvatska	Croatia
HU	Magyarország	Hungary
IT	Italia	Italy
LT	Lietuva	Lithuania
LU	Luxembourg	Luxemburg
ME	Црна Гора	Montenegro
NL	Nederland	Netherlands
PL	Polska	Poland
PT	Portugal	Portugal
RO	România	Romania
RS	Srbija/Србија	Serbia
SE	Sverige	Sweden
SI	Slovenija	Slovenia
SK	Slovensko	Slovakia

2.2 Parameterization and running of VFSSMOD

2.2.1 Treatment of soil data

The 3074 scenario / profile combinations determined previously (cf. section 2.1) were joined to the SPADE2 and SPADE14 profile/horizon data in MS Access. The resulting tables were exported as Excel tables:

- gethorizons_SPAD2_all_20240304.xlsx: profile/horizon data from SPADE2 (6979 records; Table A 4)
- gethorizons_SPAD14_all_20240304.xlsx: profile/horizon data from SPADE14 (1710 records; Table A 8)

It is important to note that these tables still contain

- R horizons (hard rock or rock rubble)
- Stone content as a variable

Out of 3074 scenario / profile combinations that should in theory be modelled, 1104 were eliminated from the above tables because of missing data (typically no texture available), which left 1970 combinations of scenario and soil profile.

Another option to deal with the 1104 combinations without texture information would have been to use the dominant topsoil texture class (TEXT1) of the Soil Typological Unit STU (not an attribute of the

profile, but of the STU) as a predictor for the missing texture class, which can then be used as input for HYPRES class pedotransfer functions. In this case only a few additional simulations would need to be done and could then assign the results to the profiles without texture information. However, the reliability of this approach was questionable, since the aggregation depth would not be the same, and the profile may have a different texture than the dominant texture of the STU.

The option to predict the missing texture using the dominant topsoil texture class (TEXT1) of the Soil Typological Unit was tested, using the 1376 scenario / profile combinations with available particle size distribution as validation data (this number translates to 1233 combinations of profile ID and STU). The effective single-horizon profiles were classified into SGDBE/HYPRES texture classes (1-5) and compared with the texture class of TEXT1. The resulting confusion matrix (n = 1233) is given in section 6.10). The most relevant measure in this case is the sensitivity (also known as recall), which is defined as the number of true positives divided by the sum of true positives and false negatives; in other words, the number of soil profiles predicted correctly to be belonging to a given texture class out of all the profiles that actually belong to this class. For texture classes 1 (C = coarse) and 3 (MF = medium fine), sensitivity is about 0.7, which can be considered acceptable. For class 2 (M = medium) sensitivity is 0.55, i.e. the probability to "predict" class 2 if there is a "true" class 2 is almost the same as for a coin toss (p = 0.5). For class 4 (F = fine) sensitivity is even worse with 0.38. Class 5 (VF = very fine) was never predicted correctly. The overall accuracy, which is the number of profiles correctly classified out of all profiles in the test set, was 0.545, i.e. very close to a random guess. In conclusion, the attribute TEXT1 cannot be considered a good predictor for the texture classes of the effective single horizon profiles. Consequently, it would be too uncertain to assign class ptf's based on the value of TEXT1 to profiles without texture information.

Of the 1970 profile/scenario combinations with complete data, 312 had an R horizon (hard rock or rock rubble) in less than 1 m depth (column maxdepth_final).

Of these 312 combinations many had very shallow profiles (although they allegedly had agricultural or horticultural use, cf. column USE):

- 112 profile/scenario combinations have an R horizon starting at < 50 cm
- 73 profile/scenario combinations have an R horizon starting at < 30 cm.

Finally it was decided to eliminate profiles shallower than 30 cm, since such soils are not suitable for mechanized agriculture (assuming that the field soil and the VFS soil have the same geological substrate and similar depth to rock). The averaging depth for the effective single-horizon profiles was set to 1 m (or beginning of hard rock, whichever is shallower).

For the valid 1897 profile/scenario combinations, effective single-horizon profiles for VFSSMOD from SPADE2 and SPADE14 profile databases were calculated as follows:

- depth-weighted arithmetic mean for soil properties (texture, bulk density, OM, stone content)
- averaging depth: min (1 m; beginning of hard rock)

The following files were produced:

- 2024_effectiveSingleHoriz_20240305b_SAV_20240504b.xlsx: final (depth-weighted) effective single-horizon profiles for modelling with VFSSMOD (1897 records = scenario/profile combinations)
- profileHorizonsMissingValues_20240305.xlsx: List of eliminated scenario / profile combinations due to missing data (1104 records)

2.2.2 Derivation of VFSMOD parameters

Profile-specific VFSMOD parameters (Table 2) were calculated from the effective single-horizon profiles using the following stepwise procedure:

- 1) Calculate Mualem-Van Genuchten parameters, using HYPRES continuous pedotransfer functions (Wösten et al., 1998) for soils within the validity limit of the HYPRES continuous ptf's ($0.5 \% < \text{SILT} < 99 \% \text{ AND } 0.5 \% < \text{CLAY} < 90 \% \text{ AND } 0.1 \% < \text{OM} < 30 \% \text{ AND } 0.5 \text{ kg/dm}^3 < \text{DB}$). For soils outside these validity limits, the HYPRES class pedotransfer functions (Wösten et al., 1998) were used
- 2) Calculate VFSMOD parameters
 - Vertical saturated conductivity VKS: use Mualem-Van Genuchten parameter K0 from HYPRES ptf's
 - Average suction at wetting front SAV: calculated by Rafael Muñoz-Carpena in Mathematica according to Neuman (1976)
 - Saturated water content OS: (use θ_s from HYPRES, corrected for stone content, assuming a stone porosity of 10 %); the reduction of OS will lead to a deeper wetting front, but it does not affect the value of SAV
 - Field capacity water content FC: read off from Van Genuchten water retention curve at pF2
 - FC is also used as initial water content OI
 - Manning's roughness coefficient RNA: refers to the surface characteristics of the VFS; depends on the vegetation and state of the VFS; RNA does not depend on the VFS soil profile nor on the field soil \rightarrow same value ($0.40 \text{ s m}^{-1/3}$) chosen for all profiles (identically to Brown et al., 2012); see also tabulated values from the VFSMOD manual (Muñoz-Carpena and Parsons, 2022) for comparison (Figure A 5)
 - Other parameters: see VFSMOD parameterization guidance (Ritter et al., 2023)

In Brown et al. (2012) the average suction at the wetting front SAV was defined as a function of the FOCUS scenario, i.e. as a property of the soil of the arable field. However, since SAV is used for simulating infiltration in the VFS, it has to be a property of the VFS soil. Hence, in our study SAV is specific to the VFS soil profile.

Of the 1897 scenario / profile combinations, there were 239 with an R horizon in less than 1 m depth. The presence of shallow R horizons implies that the assumptions of the Green-Ampt approach (homogeneous soil, no obstacles to the wetting front) are not met, unless the rocks are karstic or very fractured. An impermeable rock layer poses the same limitation to percolation as a permanent shallow water table. Hence, assuming that the R layer is impermeable, the profile can be modelled with the shallow water table option (cf. Bach et al., 2017). Note, however, that the assumption of impermeability is a worst case because many types of hard rock have fissures or cracks (e.g. granite) or a certain permeability (e.g. sandstone, limestone).

To test the impact of using the shallow water option for shallow soils on the final CDFs (90th percentile worst case profiles and predicted pesticide reduction efficiencies (ΔP)), two variants were set up in VFSMOD:

- Variant A: Profiles with hard rock in < 100 cm depth were simulated as infiltration on a soil with a limiting horizon, using the shallow water table option in VFSMOD (Muñoz-Carpena et al., 2018); no changes for the other profiles with limiting horizons > 100 cm were made, as the infiltration will not typically run that deep in normal infiltration events
- Variant B: All profiles were simulated with classical Green-Ampt infiltration (no limiting horizons in the soil)

Table 2 List of profile-specific VFSSMOD parameters

Parameter	unit	description	remarks
VKS	m s ⁻¹	vertical saturated conductivity	
SAV	m	suction at wetting front	Used only for Green-Ampt approach
FC	m ³ m ⁻³	field capacity water content of VFS soil	Used only for pesticide degradation
OS	m ³ m ⁻³	saturated water content of VFS soil	Stone content considered (assuming a stone porosity of 10 %)
OI	m ³ m ⁻³	initial water content of VFS soil	Set equal to FC
VGN	(-)	Van Genuchten n	Used only for shallow water table option
VGALPHA	m ⁻¹	Van Genuchten alpha	Used only for shallow water table option
VGM	(-)	Van Genuchten m	Used only for shallow water table option; set to 1 -1/VGM
WTD	m	water table depth	Used only for shallow water table option; Set equal to depth to hard rock

2.2.3 New versions of UH and VFSSMOD

UH (Muñoz-Carpena and Parsons, 2022; Muñoz-Carpena and Parsons, 2004) is a utility written in Fortran to create inputs for VFSSMOD: rainfall hydrographs, surface runoff hydrographs and eroded sediment loads. The name UH stands for Unit Hydrograph or Hydrologic Utility. It was already used by Brown et al. (2012) to create rainfall (.irn) and runoff (.iro) hydrographs as input for VFSSMOD. Unfortunately, the rainfall and runoff hydrographs produced by Brown et al (2012) using an older version of UH could not be retrieved anymore. Hence, they had to be recreated.

The new internal method in VFSSMOD for determining the median particle size d₅₀ (Reichenberger et al., 2023) uses peak runoff rate as an input. However, the peak runoff rate depends on the temporal resolution of the runoff hydrograph. Hence, it was necessary to make the temporal resolution of the UH output hydrographs configurable. Moreover, it was decided to use the MUSS equation (Williams, 1995) for calculating eroded sediment yield, analogously to PRZM for the FOCUS scenarios (FOCUS, 2001). These modifications required the development of a new version of UH by the VFSSMOD developer. After iterative beta-testing of the new UH version a final version was obtained UH v. 3.07, dated 27/02/2023.

The new UH v 3.07 is able to

- produce rainfall and runoff hydrographs with user-defined temporal resolution
- produce erosion estimated with MUSS equation (used in FOCUS PRZM)

Since the VFSSMOD version used by Brown et al. (2012) (v.4.2.4) several improved process descriptions were implemented in VFSSMOD. First, new pesticide trapping equations were implemented in VFSSMOD to address the concerns formulated in the MAGPIE report (Alix et al., 2017): “The regulatory status of VFSSMOD in the EU regulatory process is currently uncertain. The model is recommended for use here given its general validation status in the scientific literature and because it is able to reflect changes in buffer efficacy based on e.g. changes in antecedent moisture conditions. Additional work is recommended outside of the MAGPIE process to reach a conclusion on the regulatory acceptability of the model in the EU. A particular issue is evaluation of coupling of the basic VFSSMOD code with the

regression equation for pesticide transfer across vegetated filter strips reported by Sabbagh et al. (2009).”

To corroborate and improve the predictive capability of the Sabbagh equation, Reichenberger et al. (2019) compiled additional experimental VFS data from the available literature. The enlarged dataset (n = 244 values of relative pesticide load reduction ΔP) was used to recalibrate the Sabbagh equation, the recently proposed Chen equation (Chen et al., 2016) and a set of “reduced” Sabbagh equations with fewer independent variables. Moreover, an alternative, regression-free mass balance approach was developed and tested, building on the initial mass balance proposed in Muñoz-Carpena et al. (2015). The recalibrated Sabbagh equation fitted the observed data well (coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.819$), and its coefficients were corroborated by both a rigorous k-fold cross-validation analysis and a maximum-likelihood-based calibration and uncertainty analysis conducted with DREAM_ZS (Vrugt, 2016).

However, the regression-free mass-balance approach also fitted the observed data quite well ($R^2 = 0.741$) and much better than the old Sabbagh equation with the original coefficients ($R^2 = 0.528$). Because of its advantage of being mechanistic and its overall good predictive performance while being conservative, the mass balance approach is now recommended as the default option for regulatory modelling of pesticide trapping in VFS with VFSSMOD (Ritter et al., 2023).

The mass-balance trapping equation of Reichenberger et al. (2019) is given as:

$$\frac{\Delta P}{100\%} = \frac{\min [(V_i + K_d E_i); (\frac{\Delta Q}{100\%} V_i + \frac{\Delta E}{100\%} K_d E_i)]}{(V_i + K_d E_i)} \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

with

ΔP	relative reduction of total incoming pesticide load (%)
V_i	incoming run-on volume (L) (run-on is the overland flow entering the VFS from upslope)
K_d	linear sorption coefficient (L kg ⁻¹);
E_i	incoming eroded sediment load (kg)
ΔQ	relative reduction of total inflow (rainfall + run-on) (%)
ΔE	relative reduction of incoming eroded sediment load (%)

The minimum expression for the conservation of mass was later shown to be unnecessary, because ΔQ and ΔE cannot get larger than 100 %. This simplifies the equation to

$$\frac{\Delta P}{100\%} = \frac{(\frac{\Delta Q}{100\%} V_i + \frac{\Delta E}{100\%} K_d E_i)]}{(V_i + K_d E_i)} \quad (\text{eq. 1b})$$

The K_d in eqs. 1 and 1b is calculated in VFSSMOD as $K_d = K_{oc} * OCP/100$, with K_{oc} being the linear adsorption coefficient normalized to organic carbon (user input) and OCP the organic carbon content (%) of the eroded sediment (assumed equal to the organic carbon content of the uppermost horizon of the field soil, i.e. the soil of the R scenario parameterized in PRZM).

The second new feature in VFSSMOD was the internal calculation of median particle size d_{50} , which is the most important sediment characteristic for sediment trapping. The rationale for the development of this calculation was that the default value of $d_{50} = 20 \mu\text{m}$ chosen by Brown et al (2012) seemed too high, thus leading to an overestimation of sediment load reduction ΔE . The value of $20 \mu\text{m}$ had been chosen as a low percentile from an experimental d_{50} dataset (n = 185) which was however likely not representative of edge-of-field runoff (cf. discussion in Reichenberger et al., 2023). Since errors in

sediment trapping efficiency ΔE propagate to ΔP , for strongly-sorbing compounds an accurate prediction of ΔE is crucial for a reliable prediction of ΔP . Reichenberger et al. (2023) first compiled an extensive dataset of 93 d50 values and 17 candidate explanatory variables compiled from heterogeneous data sources and methods, and subsequently derived an improved dynamic d50 parameterization equation for use in regulatory VFS scenarios. The dataset was analysed first using machine learning techniques (Random Forest, Gradient Boosting) and Global Sensitivity Analysis (GSA) as a dimension reduction technique and to identify potential interactions between explanatory variables. Using the knowledge gained, a parsimonious multiple regression equation with 6 predictors was developed and thoroughly tested. Since three of the predictors are event-specific (eroded sediment yield, rainfall intensity and peak runoff rate), predicted d50 vary dynamically across event magnitudes and intensities. The internal, dynamic d50 calculation option is now recommended as the standard option for regulatory modelling with VFSMOD (Ritter et al., 2023).

The third new feature, the new leaching / remobilization algorithm (Muñoz-Carpena et al., *in preparation*; Muñoz-Carpena et al., 2022) was developed to improve the accuracy of the calculation of pesticide residues in the mixing layer of the VFS soil at the end of a runoff event as well as the accuracy of the pesticide mass remobilized at the next runoff event. Leaching in the VFS is now calculated fully mechanistically using an analytical solution of the chemical convective-dispersive transport equation (CDE) with sorption under Green-Ampt infiltration (Huang and van Genuchten, 1995). The key features of the new remobilization approach (Figure 2) are that i) only dissolved pesticides in the mixing layer are remobilized, and ii) non-remobilized pesticide residues do not disappear, but are added to the incoming pesticide mass trapped in the mixing layer and are thus carried over to the next event, considering degradation. However, in this study remobilization was not relevant because only one single event was simulated, i.e. no series of events like in FOCUS step4.

Figure 2 Updates VFSMOD approach for pesticide residues. Source: Muñoz-Carpena et al. (2022).

Finally, a shallow water table option (Muñoz-Carpena et al., 2018; Lauvernet and Muñoz-Carpena, 2018) has already been available for several years. This option allows simulating the impact of a permanent or seasonal shallow water table on VFS efficiency. Moreover, the option can also be used to simulate the impact of a shallow impermeable rock layer. The basic concept of the SWINGO algorithm (Shallow Water table INFiltration algorithm; Muñoz-Carpena et al., 2018) is the following: In the first phase, infiltration is calculated using a time-explicit infiltration solution based on a combination of

approaches by Salvucci and Entekhabi (1995) and Chu (1997). Once the wetting front reaches the water table (i.e. the VFS profile is completely saturated), the boundary condition changes. The infiltration rate at the soil surface is then controlled by lateral subsurface flow, with the subsurface flow rate following Dupuit-Forchheimer assumptions (Muñoz-Carpena et al., 2018).

During preliminary VFSSMOD simulations numerical problems with snowmelt events (only relevant for FOCUS R1 scenario) emerged. The reason was that these events do not have rainfall, while a mean rainfall rate is needed for the d50 algorithm. Moreover, there was a problem with the .owq output files: Sometimes they contained numbers having negative exponents with three digits, which were then not recognized as numbers during the postprocessing in Python. Iterative beta-testing of the new VFSSMOD version resulted in a final, consolidated version: vfm.exe v.4.5.2, dated 21/03/2023. The new version also contains a modified algorithm to determine the number of numerical nodes N for the numerical solution of overland flow:

$$N = 90/99 (VL - 1) + 11$$
with VL being the VFS length in flow direction (m)

2.2.4 Setup and running of VFSSMOD simulations

VFSSMOD v. 4.5.2 was run for all 1897 valid combinations of FOCUS scenario and soil profile for example rainfall/runoff events, closely following the method of Brown et al. (2012).

First, eight rainfall/runoff events (two for each R scenario) were created with the tool UH v. 3.07 (Univ. Florida) using the following settings:

- Rainfall volume: 30 mm
- Event duration: 1 h / 8 h
- Slope length: 100 m
- Runoff and erosion parameters according to Brown et al. (2012) (see Table 6 in Brown et al., 2012)
- Erosion calculation with MUSS equation (like in FOCUS PRZM); this equation was not available in earlier versions of UH
- Temporal resolution of created rainfall hydrographs (.irn) and field runoff hydrographs (.iro): 15 min

UH input and output files can be found in the digital annex (see section 6.11).

Brown et al. (2002) selected a rainfall volume of 30 mm in order to produce sufficient surface runoff so that complete infiltration in the VFS occurred only rarely. The rainfall durations of 1 h and 8 h were chosen by Brown et al (2012) for the following reasons: The high-intensity, short-duration event (30 mm in 1 hour) was conceptualised as a convective rainstorm event as it occasionally occurs in European summers, while the low-intensity, long-duration event (30 mm in 8 hours) was conceptualised as a depression-led, advective rainfall event.

VFSSMOD was run for two example compounds ($K_{oc} = 100 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$ and 10000 L kg^{-1}) and a VFS length in flow direction (“VFS width”) VL of 10 m. Hence, in total 1897 scenario/profile combinations * 2 event durations * 2 K_{oc} values * 2 variants (A and B) = 15176 VFSSMOD simulations were performed (1 simulation = 1 event).

The two K_{oc} values were chosen by Brown et al. (2012) to reflect contrasting sorption behaviour. While for $K_{oc} = 100 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$ the compound will be predominantly transported in the dissolved phase of the surface runoff, for $K_{oc} = 10000 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$ the dissolved and particle-bound fractions will be of the same order of magnitude.

In contrast to the simulations of Brown et al. (2012) new process descriptions were used that did not exist in the old VFSSMOD version (v. 4.2.4) used by Brown et al. (2012) (see section 2.2.3):

- trapping equation: mass balance approach (Reichenberger et al., 2019; Muñoz-Carpena et al., 2015)
- median particle size d50: internal calculation with multiple regression equation (Reichenberger et al., 2023)
- improved leaching/remobilization algorithm (Muñoz-Carpena et al., in preparation; Muñoz-Carpena et al., 2022)

Moreover, a minor change was made to the parameter SS (average spacing of grass stems): The value was changed from 1.63 cm (corresponding to ryegrass (perennial); Muñoz-Carpena and Parsons, 2022) to a slightly more conservative value of 2.15 cm (corresponding to a grass mixture; Muñoz-Carpena and Parsons, 2022). For the VFSSMOD simulations, a tailing time of 100 % was added to the .irn file in order to make sure that all runoff water has either infiltrated or run off before the end of the simulation. VFSSMOD simulations were created, launched and postprocessed using the knoell tool swan2pyVFSSMOD. swan2pyVFSSMOD is a Python wrapper around VFSSMOD which reproduces the functionalities of SWAN-VFSSMOD. The target variable was the relative reduction of pesticide load (ΔP) by the VFS. All VFSSMOD input and output can be found in the digital annex.

2.3 Spatial aggregation and determination of 90th percentile worst case profiles

The workflow to determine 90th percentile worst case profiles was:

- 1) Calculate area of scenario/profile combinations
- 2) Calculate spatial CDFs of target variable ΔP (pesticide load reduction efficiency) for each combination of FOCUS scenario and treatment
 - 4 R scenarios
 - 2 different Koc values (100 and 10000 L kg⁻¹)
 - 2 event durations (1 h and 8 h)
 - 2 VFSSMOD variants (A and B)
 - 2 spatial variants: FOCUS scenario shapes clipped with CORINE Land Cover class 2 or not→ 64 CDFs
- 3) Extract profile that corresponds to the 10th spatial percentile of ΔP (90th percentile worst case)

The procedure was implemented and performed in R.
All created CDFs can be found in the digital annex.

2.3.1 Calculation of area fractions for each soil profile

Calculating area fractions of soil profiles per Soil Mapping unit (SMU) was challenging and time-consuming, due to

- complex and different data structures of SPADE2 and SPADE14 profile databases
- occurrence of duplicates (both in SPADE2 and SPADE14 identical profiles with different IDs occur)
- land use in SPADE14 only being described in text form → a script for assigning SPADE2 land use code had to be developed

First, the textual descriptions of land use (field LU of EST_PROF tables from SPADE14 database) were classified according to the 23 numeric land use codes of SPADE2 (see Hannam et al., 2009, p. 25) using an R script (see sections 6.7.2 for the general workflow and 0 for the code (script recodeLUspade14.R)).

The calculation of areas for each soil / scenario combination is partly based on an R script by Nils Kehrein (Bayer). However, several modifications and additions were made to the code. A fully transparent and reproducible procedure is in place now (see sections 6.7.3 for the general workflow and 0 for the code (script import_extended.R)).

The following rules (similar to those used by Hannam et al. (2009)) were used to assign area fractions covered by a given profile within a STU, considering the dominant and secondary land uses of the STU (USE_DOM and USE_SEC, respectively) and the actual land use of the profile (USE):

- 1) If USE = USE_DOM and USE_DOM is not 0 (i.e. dominant land use is known) and USE_SEC = 0 (i.e. secondary land use unknown or non-existing), the profile is assigned an area fraction of 0.8
- 2) Else if USE = USE_DOM and USE_DOM is not 0 and USE_SEC is not 0 (i.e. there is a secondary land use), the profile is assigned an area fraction of 0.6
- 3) Else if USE = USE_SEC and USE_SEC is not 0, the profile is assigned an area fraction of 0.3
- 4) Else the profile is assigned an area fraction of 0.1.
- 5) In the case that there is more than one profile in the same STU with the same land use, the area fractions calculated above are evenly distributed over these profiles.
- 6) Finally the area fraction of the SMU covered by the soil profile is calculated.

The result of the procedure is a table of area fractions (see Table A 15 for the list of variables). Two variants have been produced:

- CLC_link_table.csv (with intersection with CORINE Land Cover; see section 2.1)
- noCLC_link_table.csv (without intersection with CORINE Land Cover)

The two tables are included in the digital annex.

2.3.2 Spatial aggregation to CDFs

In the next step, spatial cumulative distribution functions of the target variable ΔP were calculated using the area fractions calculated above. The general workflow is described in section 6.7.4, and the code (createSpatialCDF.R) can be found in the digital annex.

As a plausibility check, for each FOCUS scenario the fraction of the scenario polygon area that is covered by the corresponding CDF was also calculated.

2.3.3 Determination of 90th percentile worst case profiles and associated parameters

After the CDFs had been created, the next steps were:

- Determine profile that corresponds to the 10th spatial percentile of ΔP (90th percentile worst case). For this we used a binary search algorithm in R.
- Extract scenario parameters of selected profiles using MS Access.

The general workflow is described in section 6.7.5, and the code (profileID_90th_PPerc.R) can be found in the digital annex (see section 6.11).

2.4 Comparison of new CDFs with previous SWAN-VFSMOD scenarios / VFSMOD version

A series of test runs (4 FOCUS R scenarios * 2 Koc values * 2 durations) were done with the VFSMOD version (v. 4.2.4) and parameterization from SWAN 5.01. The objective was to check how conservative assessments with SWAN 5.01 are in comparison with the new spatial CDFs, and how ΔP will change if we switch from SWAN 5.01 to the 10th percentile of the new CDFs.

The settings of the 16 test runs were as follows:

- same v fsm.exe (v. 4.2.4) as in the portable version of SWAN 5.01
- Koc 100 and 10000 L kg⁻¹
- 30 mm rainfall, rainfall durations 1 h and 8 h, VL = 10 m (like in Brown et al., 2012)
- 4 FOCUS R scenarios with the same VFSMOD parameterization as in SWAN 5.01

- same runoff and rainfall hydrographs (.iro and .irn) as in the simulations used for the new CDFs
- same eroded sediment load and pesticide input

These results were compared with the spatial CDFs obtained using the current v_{fsm}.exe (v. 4.5.2) and recommended parameterization (variant B = classical Green-Ampt for all profiles).

To isolate the effect of the different trapping equations (old Sabbagh equation (Sabbagh et al., 2009) vs. mass balance approach (Reichenberger et al., 2019)), we also calculated ΔP according to the mass balance approach for the 16 test simulations. Subsequently we

- i) compared ΔP of the 16 test runs with ΔP of the 10th percentile profiles from the new CDFs.
- ii) determined the position of the 16 test simulations on the corresponding spatial CDFs produced with the new approach (using the script `get_CumAreapercent_of_old_VFSMOD.R`; the script is included in the digital annex (see section 6.11))

2.5 Analysis with regard to soil texture

In this report we aim to address the standing statement on the SWAN page at ESDAC (<https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/projects/swan>): “As the uncertainty whether the mitigation being modelled with VFSmod is achieved for all the other soil textures that the FOCUS scenarios cover still has to be independently evaluated, VFSmod has only rarely been accepted for use in EU level assessments and decision making.” Prior to the development of this report and to ensure that its scope addresses the comment, we engaged EFSA personnel to identify the best way to address this comment. The discussion revealed that this could be properly addressed by demonstrating “a best available estimate of a 90th spatial percentile of a target trapping effectiveness, for each complete area in each of the maps showing spatial area covered by each FOCUS runoff scenario” (EFSA expert comment, 07/08/2024). This fits very well with the main scope of this study: to derive VFS scenarios for SWAN-VFSMOD which, for each FOCUS R scenario, reflect an overall 90th percentile worst case (see section 2.3).

In addition, to provide additional insights and to demonstrate the robustness of the selected scenarios, we complemented the analysis by segmenting the VFSMOD results also with respect to texture classes. Preliminary results (still without spatial weighting) were presented and discussed at the VFSMOD workshop in Piacenza on 03/09/2024 (<https://symposiumpesticide.org/xvii-pesticide-symposium-piacenza-workshop/>). There it was agreed by the participants (including EFSA representatives) and included in the workshop resolutions that the final results of the analysis should be included in this report and an upcoming peer-reviewed publication. For this analysis, the following procedure was followed:

- First, a SGDBE texture class (Figure 3; Le Bas et al., 1998; CEC, 1985) was assigned to each soil profile simulated with VFSMOD. Note that these are the same texture classes for which the HYPRES class pedotransfer functions (Wösten et al., 1998) have been defined. Profiles with an organic matter content greater than 30 % were classified as “organic” (O).
- Subsequently descriptive statistics of ΔP were calculated for each combination of scenario, texture class, Koc and event duration). Spatial weighting was applied in the calculation of these statistics, i.e. each scenario / profile combination was weighted with its area.
- Finally, the descriptive statistics were plotted as boxplots and compared with ΔP obtained for the 90th percentile worst case profiles (cf. section 2.3.3). In addition, “pooled” boxplots (i.e. boxplots combining all 4 R scenarios) were created and compared with the 10th percentile of ΔP of the combined CDF over all scenarios. Also these boxplots were spatially weighted. Apart from the graphical comparison, for each texture class also the cumulative area fraction corresponding to the ΔP of the 90th percentile worst case profile was determined using a binary search algorithm.

Figure 3 The SGDBE texture triangle. Source: https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Texture-classes-after-CEC-1985-Expressing-lateral-variability-BULLET-A-STU-can-have_fig2_237642627

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Area covered by CDFs

For the EU27, 48-61 % of the FOCUS scenario shapefile area are covered by the new spatial CDFs (Figure 4). These numbers are plausible because i) not all STUs have profiles, and ii) profiles usually cover only a part of the STU. There is no systematic difference in area coverage between the variants CORINE and noCORINE (cf. section 2.1).

Figure 4 Area fractions of FOCUS scenario shapefiles (for the extent of the EU27) covered by the new spatial CDFs.

There is still an open question whether CORINE land cover should be considered at all in the area calculation, i.e. whether an intersection with CLC class 2 (agricultural land) should be made or not. This issue is not discussed in Brown et al. (2012).

The problem is that land use from the SGDBE (the dominant and secondary land use of each STU in the `stu_sgdb.dbf`) has already been considered in the derivation of the FOCUS scenario shapefiles (FOCUS, 2001; Hollis, 2007): “Having identified those STU’s with soil characteristics representative of each Scenario, it was then necessary to ensure that each of the selected STU’s in the 1:1,000,000 scale Soil Geographic Database of Europe are also associated with at least some of the crops that characterise each scenario. This was also done through the STU attribute database of the Soil Geographic Database of Europe. In this database, each STU is characterised by two land use classes defining its ‘dominant’ and ‘secondary’ land use. The land use classes included in the Soil Geographic Database of Europe are defined in Table 3.4-1 and those used to identify the associated STU’s for each Scenario are shown in Table 3.4-3, together with the range of crops defined for each scenario (see section 3.3). The distribution of each Scenario within Europe was then mapped using the ArcView GIS software. Initially, the soil types corresponding to each scenario were selected by identifying all map units in the 1:1,000,000 scale Soil Geographic Database of Europe that contained an STU with attributes corresponding to those defined in Tables 3.4-2 and 3.4-3.”

This means that the FOCUS scenario shapefiles only contain SMUs which have at least one STU which has at least one of the land uses listed in Table 3.4-3 of the FOCUS report as dominant or secondary land use.

- For R1: arable land, horticulture, vineyards, arboriculture/orchards, industrial crops, vegetables
- For R2 and R3: same as for R1, plus artificial soils for orchards
- For R4: same as for R2 and R3, plus olive trees

Hence, land use has already been considered in the FOCUS scenario shapefiles. However, as follows from the above rules, the FOCUS scenario shapefiles also contain STUs without any of the specified land uses, and STUs with only one of these land uses. In other words, as highlighted by FOCUS (2001), “The maps do not mean that the scenarios are relevant to 100% of the areas highlighted. Rather they indicate that in any of the areas highlighted, some part of the agricultural landscape corresponds to the soil, climate and at least one of the cropping characteristics of the specified scenario”. This implies that the area of the FOCUS scenario shapefiles contains also a significant area with non-relevant land uses.

Since the STUs are not localized within the SMU polygons, the intersection with CORINE Land Cover does not remove non-relevant STUs. However, it yields a more relevant total polygon area of each scenario. The spatial aggregation procedure to produce CDFs (section 6.7.4) only considers STUs that are linked to a SPADE profile. Land uses associated to a given SPADE profile are taken into account with their correct area fractions, however, they are not filtered (i.e. all valid SPADE profiles are taken into account regardless whether their land use is agricultural or not). However, filtering out non-agricultural SPADE profiles after the intersection with CORINE would constitute double-accounting of land use.

Another methodological option would have been to not use CORINE Land Cover, but then to filter the SPADE profiles instead and use only those with relevant land uses. However, the aim was to stay as close as possible to the method of Brown et al. (2012), who did not filter the SPADE profiles according to land use either. Moreover, the soil under a VFS does not necessarily need to have been under arable or grassland use before. It could also have been under forest or shrub cover before, for example. Hence, to maintain the consistency with Brown et al. (2012), we recommend to keep the intersection with CORINE Land Cover while not filtering the SPADE profiles according to land use.

3.2 Spatial CDFs

At total of 64 CDFs has been created, as a result of the combination of the following factors:

- FOCUS R scenarios (4)
- CORINE vs. no CORINE (2)
- Rainfall duration: 1 h vs. 8 h (2)
- Koc: 100 L kg⁻¹ vs. 10000 L kg⁻¹ (2)
- Variant A vs. Variant B (2)

All CDFs can be found in the digital annex in graphical (.png) and tabular (.csv) format. The effect of the different factors is discussed in the following.

3.2.1 CORINE vs. noCORINE

The intersection of a given FOCUS scenario shapefile with CORINE Land Cover only affects the areas of the individual SMU/profile combinations (and hence the total area and shape of the CDF), but it has no relation to the VFSMOD results and hence no effect on the ranking of soil profiles.

Figure 5 Example CDF (R3, Koc = 100 L kg⁻¹, duration = 8 h, and variant B) with (top) and without (bottom) intersection with CORINE Land Cover (CLC) 2018 class 2.

Overall, the effect of the intersection with CLC on the CDF is small (Figure 5). However, sometimes it can lead to a different 90th percentile worst case profile (Table A 20).

3.2.2 Effect of Rainfall duration

Since the rainfall volume was always the same (30 mm) and UH uses the Curve Number approach, the event duration did not affect the surface runoff volume generated by UH. However, it affected both rainfall and runoff intensity in the hydrographs produced by UH.

Figure 6 Example CDF (FOCUS R1, intersect with CLC 2018 class 2, Koc = 100 L kg⁻¹, variant B, duration = 1 h (top) and 8 h (bottom)).

For the scenario/profile combinations simulated with VFSMOD, the higher rainfall and runoff intensities for 1 h duration led to lower infiltration and pesticide trapping efficiencies, and also to a

different ranking of profiles than for 8 h duration. Consequently the CDFs look quite different for the two different event durations (Figure 6).

3.2.3 Effect of Koc

The Koc had no influence on the ranking of profiles with respect to ΔP . The reason is that the organic carbon content of the eroded sediment, which is needed to compute Kd in the trapping equation of Reichenberger et al. (2019) (eq. 1b), comes from the field soil and hence is the same for all simulations for the same R scenario. Moreover, for the predicted ΔP there was mainly a shift on the x axis between $K_{oc} = 100 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$ and $K_{oc} = 10000 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$. Consequently, the Koc had hardly any effect on the shape of the CDFs (Figure 7).

Figure 7 Example CDF (FOCUS R4, intersection with CLC 2018 class 2, duration = 1 h, variant B, Koc = 100 L kg⁻¹ (top) and 10000 L kg⁻¹ (bottom)).

3.2.4 Variant A vs. Variant B

The difference between variant A and variant B consists only in how soil profiles with hard rock in less than 1 m depth are simulated (cf. section 2.2.2). Effects on the shape of the CDFs for an event duration of 1 hour were very small (Figure 8; Figure 9). This can be explained by the fact that for high-intensity rainfall infiltration is largely controlled by the vertical saturated conductivity (VKS). However, for Variant A different 90th percentile worst-case profiles were obtained than for Variant B. Predicted ΔP values for the 90th percentile worst-case profiles were very similar between variant A and variant B, though (differences in ΔP ranged between 0.0 and 2.2 % for CORINE, and between 0.0 and 3.8 % for noCORINE).

For 8 h duration visible differences at the lower end of the CDFs could be observed (Figure 10; Figure 11). This is normal because shallow soils are typically concentrated in the lower end of the CDF. Differences in ΔP for the 90th percentile worst case profiles ranged between 0.1 and 28.5 % for CORINE, and between 0.1 and 31.4 % for noCORINE.

Figure 8 Example CDF (FOCUS R4, intersection with CLC 2018 class 2, duration = 1 h, Koc = 100 L kg⁻¹, variant A (top) and variant B (bottom)).

Figure 9 Example CDF (FOCUS R4, intersection with CLC 2018 class 2, duration = 1 h, Koc = 10000 L kg⁻¹, variant A (top) and variant B (bottom)).

Figure 10 Example CDF (FOCUS R4, intersection with CLC 2018 class 2, duration = 8 h, Koc = 100 L kg⁻¹, variant A (top) and variant B (bottom)).

Figure 11 Example CDF (FOCUS R4, intersection with CLC 2018 class 2, duration = 8 h, Koc = 10000 L kg⁻¹, variant A (top) and variant B (bottom)).

An overview of the 90th percentile worst case profiles determined for the 64 CDFs is given in R1234_90th_perc_profiles_with_VFSMOD_params_noWT_20240610.xlsx in the digital annex (see section 6.11). The main results can be summarized as follows:

- For all 32 combinations of scenario, CORINE/noCORINE, Koc and duration, the 90th percentile worst case profile is different between variant A and variant B.

- For variant A, in 20 out of 32 cases the 90th percentile worst-case profile was indeed one with depth to hard rock < 1 m.
- For 1 h rainfall duration, deltaP (%) was only marginally different between variants A and B.
- For 8 h rainfall duration, deltaP (%) was slightly or moderately different between variants A and B for R2-R4, with the largest difference being observed for R4. Differences were marginal for R1.

3.3 Final choice of scenario

64 CDFs of ΔP have been created. However, only four are needed. Finally, the combination $K_{oc} = 100 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$ / duration = 8 h / variant B / CORINE has been selected for the new SWAN-VFSMOD scenarios to be included in SWAN 5.2, for the following reasons:

- $K_{oc} = 100 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$ is more relevant for most substances on the market than $K_{oc} = 10000 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$
- duration = 8 h is closer to rainfall intensities in FOCUS_{sw} than 1 h
- variant B: classical Green-Ampt for all profiles
 - runs much faster than variant A (this becomes important when FOCUS repair becomes official and the evaluation period is increased to 20 years)
 - is easier to set up in SWAN than variant A
 - since very shallow soils have been removed, the obstacle to infiltration posed by hard rock horizons is only relevant for large rainfall/runoff events, which are rather infrequent (for instance, the return period of a 30 mm rainfall event in FOCUS_{sw} is 1.3 years for R1 and 1.1 years for R3 and R4; only for R2 it is below 1 year)
- Intersection with CORINE Land Cover (CLC) class 2: see discussion in section 3.1

The 90th percentile worst-case profiles and their parameters for the proposed combination are presented in Table 3. There are only four profile-specific VFSMOD parameters

- vertical saturated conductivity VKS
- saturated water content OS
- field capacity water content FC
- average suction at wetting front SAV

Table 3 90th percentile worst-case profiles and profile-specific VFSMOD parameters for the proposed combination and the four R scenarios

FOCUS R scenario	profile and position on CDF			profile-specific VFSMOD parameters			
	Profile ID	ΔP ¹⁾	cum. area fraction ¹⁾	VKS	SAV	OS	FC
		%	%	m s^{-1}	m	$\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$	$\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$
R1	FR27	20.63	9.99	5.94E-07	0.078	0.384	0.341
R2	330549_1	56.32	10.00	1.88E-06	0.048	0.451	0.356
R3	330562_1	29.97	10.38	1.07E-06	0.064	0.428	0.352
R4	ES29	44.83	9.88	2.01E-06	0.015	0.413	0.349

¹⁾ for the following settings: use CORINE, $K_{oc} = 100 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$, rainfall = 30 mm, event duration = 8 h, VL = 10 m, variant B (classical Green-Ampt)

3.4 Comparison of new CDFs with previous SWAN-VFSMOD scenarios / old VFSMOD version

An overview of predicted trapping efficiencies for the example events (30 mm rainfall, VL = 10 m, duration 1 or 8 h) is given in Table 4. The main findings are:

- For $K_{oc} = 100 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$, the mass balance trapping equation always yielded substantially lower pesticide reduction efficiency (ΔP) than the old Sabbagh equation (Sabbagh et al., 2009).
- For $K_{oc} = 10000 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$, the mass balance trapping equation yielded on average slightly higher pesticide reduction efficiency (ΔP) than the old, now deprecated trapping equation of Sabbagh et al. (2009), largely due to R3. R3 is the R scenario with the highest topsoil clay content, and clay has a strongly negative effect on ΔP in the old Sabbagh equation.
- For $K_{oc} = 100 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$, the new 10th percentile profiles always yielded substantially lower (more conservative) ΔP than the old scenarios with the old VFSMOD version v.4.2.4 (mean difference of ΔP 39.6 % for CORINE and 36.5 for noCORINE)
- For $K_{oc} = 10000 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$, ΔP of the new 10th percentile profiles and ΔP of the old scenarios / VFSMOD version were on average the same (mean difference of ΔP 0.78 % for CORINE and 0.07 for noCORINE). In three out of eight cases the new profiles yielded higher ΔP than the old scenarios / VFSMOD version; however, as the ΔP obtained with the mass balance show, this was not due to the hydrology, but due to the old trapping equation of Sabbagh et al. (2009) used in SWAN 5.

An overview of the positions (i.e. cumulative probabilities) of the old SWAN/VFSMOD scenario on the CDFs is given in Table 5. The main results can be summarized as follows:

- When the trapping efficiencies for the 16 test runs were calculated with the old Sabbagh equation, positions of the test runs on the new CDFs of ΔP were always higher than 10 % (i.e. less conservative than the 90th percentile worst case), except for three cases where the Sabbagh equation yielded a cumulative probability of zero or almost zero, and two cases where the mass balance approach yielded a cumulative probability of 8.5 % (for noCORINE).
- Positions on the CDF were considerably less variable with the mass balance trapping equation than with the old Sabbagh equation
- CORINE vs. no CORINE had only a slight influence on the position on the CDF.

It has to be noted that the results of this exercise cannot be completely extrapolated to the SWAN-VFSMOD tool, because in this simulation exercise we used realistic rainfall and runoff hydrographs generated with the UH tool (analogously to Brown et al., 2012). Results may be slightly different with the rectangular, low-intensity rainfall hydrographs from SWAN (as long as the daily rainfall volume does not exceed 48 mm, rainfall intensity in SWAN is only 2 mm/h due to the disaggregation method used for converting daily PRZM output to the hourly .p2t file).

However, this analysis provided enough evidence to conclude that the new SWAN-VFSMOD scenarios are overall more conservative than the old ones.

Table 4 Pesticide reduction efficiencies (ΔP) predicted with old SWAN-VFSMOD scenarios and old v fsm executable, and 10th percentile profiles of the new CDFs ¹⁾ created using the new v fsm executable

FOCUS scenario		event duration	pesticide reduction efficiency predicted with new 10 th percentile profiles (variant B ²⁾)		pesticide reduction efficiency predicted with old SWAN-VFSMOD scenarios and old v fsm executable		difference (old VFSMOD with Sabbagh) - 10 th percentile profile		difference (old VFSMOD with mass balance) - 10 th percentile profile		
			CORINE	noCORINE	Sabbagh eq.	mass balance	CORINE	noCORINE	CORINE	noCORINE	
	Koc		ΔP	ΔP	ΔP	ΔP	difference (ΔP)	difference (ΔP)	difference (ΔP)	difference (ΔP)	
	L kg ⁻¹	h	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	
R1	10000	1	68.78	68.78	70.62	72.89	1.85	1.85	4.11	4.11	
		8	74.26	74.31	80.93	79.06	6.66	6.61	4.80	4.75	
R2		1	79.07	79.55	76.17	83.19	-2.90	-3.38	4.13	3.64	
		8	90.03	94.82	100.00	93.66	9.97	5.18	3.64	-1.15	
R3		1	69.72	69.80	52.91	73.68	-16.81	-16.88	3.96	3.88	
		8	77.94	78.18	65.52	81.32	-12.43	-12.66	3.38	3.14	
R4		1	52.12	52.12	64.69	59.55	12.57	12.57	7.44	7.44	
		8	70.82	70.82	78.13	72.46	7.30	7.30	1.64	1.64	
R1		100	1	9.15	9.15	62.35	15.18	53.20	53.20	6.04	6.04
			8	20.63	20.80	72.65	32.71	52.02	51.85	12.09	11.92
R2	1		21.97	23.93	68.68	26.37	46.71	44.75	4.40	2.45	
	8		56.32	77.68	94.26	71.47	37.95	16.58	15.16	-6.21	
R3	1		11.56	11.80	44.69	17.70	33.13	32.89	6.14	5.90	
	8		29.97	30.78	57.30	38.69	27.33	26.51	8.72	7.91	
R4	1		12.75	12.75	55.11	23.67	42.36	42.36	10.92	10.92	
	8		44.83	44.83	68.54	47.58	23.71	23.71	2.75	2.75	

¹⁾ For a 30 mm rainfall event and VL = 10 m

²⁾ Variant B: classical Green-Ampt infiltration for all profiles

Table 5 Positions of old SWAN/VFSMOD scenarios (with old VFSMOD executable) on new CDFs ¹⁾

FOCUS scenario			Results of old SWAN/VFSMOD scenarios with old VFSMOD exe					Positions of old scenarios / exe on new CDFs (variant B)				
			relative reduction of total inflow	relative reduction of eroded sed. load	relative reduction of incoming runoff	relative reduction of pesticide load		with Sabbagh et al. (2009)		with mass balance approach		
						Sabbagh eq.	mass balance	CORINE	noCORINE	CORINE	noCORINE	
	Koc	duration	ΔQ ²⁾	ΔE ²⁾	ΔR ²⁾	ΔP	ΔP	cum. area fraction	cum. area fraction	cum. area fraction	cum. area fraction	
	L kg ⁻¹	h	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	
R1	10000	1	13.23	98.30	-25.40	70.62	72.89	43.77	40.37	76.40	73.96	
		8	31.15	99.51	3.99	80.93	79.06	44.25	40.39	37.46	34.94	
R2		1	23.68	99.30	-18.11	76.17	83.19	0.02	0.01	22.85	16.51	
		8	70.42	99.95	54.17	100.00	93.66	98.80	98.73	10.51	8.50	
R3		1	15.77	97.50	-22.90	52.91	73.68	0.00	0.00	56.38	54.13	
		8	37.22	99.47	12.05	65.52	81.32	0.00	0.01	22.82	21.29	
R4		1	22.97	99.07	-7.52	64.69	59.55	68.13	67.75	50.71	47.85	
		8	47.10	99.85	26.03	78.13	72.46	20.30	20.46	11.91	12.50	
R1		100	1	13.23	98.30	-25.40	62.35	15.18	99.93	99.94	44.98	41.35
			8	31.15	99.51	3.99	72.65	32.71	98.40	98.13	35.36	32.53
R2			1	23.68	99.30	-18.11	68.68	26.37	71.88	65.72	16.24	12.19
			8	70.42	99.95	54.17	94.26	71.47	23.20	16.71	10.51	8.50
R3	1		15.77	97.50	-22.90	44.69	17.70	89.68	89.79	33.23	33.31	
	8		37.22	99.47	12.05	57.30	38.69	57.26	55.28	20.76	18.52	
R4	1		22.97	99.07	-7.52	55.11	23.67	91.30	90.65	38.82	36.18	
	8		47.10	99.85	26.03	68.54	47.58	32.35	30.55	11.91	12.50	

¹⁾ For a 30 mm rainfall event and VL = 10 m

²⁾ ΔQ , ΔE and ΔR for the old SWAN/VFSMOD scenarios are only given as additional information to ease the interpretation of predicted ΔP .

3.5 Analysis with regard to soil texture

In the following, only the comparison for the combination of factors is discussed from which the proposed scenarios for SWAN-VFSMOD were selected: Koc 100 L kg⁻¹, duration 8 h, CORINE, variant B (classical Green-Ampt). However, the whole set of boxplots and corresponding tables (.xlsx) can be found in the digital annex. Results for the individual scenarios are shown in Figure 12 and Table 6, while the “pooled” results (all scenarios combined) are shown in Figure 13 and Table 7.

From the individual FOCUS scenarios, the comparison of the spatially weighted boxplots of ΔP for the five SGDBE (or HYPRES) texture classes with the 10th percentile of ΔP (i.e. the 90th percentile worst case ΔP) of the whole CDF (all texture classes), yielded that for most combinations of scenario and texture class the ΔP for the 90th percentile worst case profiles are conservative (Table 6). Only for R1 / VF (very fine; > 60 % clay) and R2 / MF (medium fine; silt) the class median of ΔP was lower than the 10th spatial percentile of ΔP for the whole CDF (Figure 12). However, these texture classes occur only rarely ($n = 11$ and 7 , respectively) and cover only a small area fraction of the respective scenario. The number of organic soils (class O) was too small for any interpretation. Note that since both the boxplots and the horizontal lines come from the same statistical population (the spatial CDFs of ΔP for all simulated soils belonging to the R scenario), by definition there must be data points below the red horizontal line which correspond to 10 % of the area of the CDF. The “intersection point” of the red line and the boxplots, i.e. the positions of the 10th percentile ΔP for the whole CDF on the CDFs for the individual texture classes is given in Table 6. For several combinations of scenario and texture class the cumulative area percentage of the intersection point was greater than 10 %. However, this is normal, because some texture classes have higher vulnerability than others. It is virtually impossible that an overall 90th percentile worst case over all soils (the red line in the boxplots) could constitute a 90th percentile worst case also for each texture class. For some texture classes, the cumulative area percentage will be higher than 10 %, and for others lower (or even 0). While it would be possible to shift the red line downwards to obtain a $\geq 90^{\text{th}}$ percentile worst case also for the most vulnerable texture class, this would result in an extreme overall worst case. For instance, for R1 / class VF the 10th percentile ΔP is 15.154 %. For the whole CDF for R1 (all texture classes together) this ΔP value corresponds to a cumulative area percentage of 0.56 %. We would thus have an overall 99.44th percentile worst case.

Results for the “pooled” boxplots (boxplots combining all 4 R scenarios) were similar to those for the individual scenarios. Only for the relative rare and extreme texture classes “medium fine” and “very fine” the class median of ΔP was (slightly and moderately, resp.) lower than the 10th spatial percentile of ΔP for the whole CDF (Figure 13). The cumulative area percentages of the intersection point were 54.7 % for “medium fine” and 73.3 % for “very fine” (Table 7). For the other texture classes they were close to or exactly zero. If we shift the red line downwards we observe similar patterns as for the CDFs per scenario: For instance, for class MF (all scenarios together) the 10th percentile ΔP is 19.842 %. For the whole CDF (all scenarios and texture classes together) this ΔP value corresponds to a cumulative area percentage of 2.66 %, i.e. an overall 97.34th percentile worst case.

In summary, this analysis confirms that the approach of selecting overall 90th percentile worst case soil profiles for the VFS scenarios is reasonable. Some texture classes have higher vulnerability than others. The general ranking of ΔP (C > M > F > MF > VF) reflects the hydraulic parameter sets obtained with the HYPRES pedotransfer functions; notably predicted saturated conductivity is on average lowest for soils with texture classes MF and VF.

Figure 12 Spatially weighted boxplots of predicted pesticide trapping efficiency (ΔP) according to texture class for all simulated profiles for each scenario (Koc 100 L kg⁻¹, duration 8 h, CORINE, variant B). Boxes: 25th and 75th percentiles, whiskers: min and max. Spatial weighting with with area of the scenario/profile combination was applied. Horizontal line: 10th percentile ΔP (90th percentile worst case) of whole CDF (all texture classes) for option CORINE. Texture classes are C = Coarse, M = medium, MF = medium fine, F = fine, VF = very fine, O = organic. The sample size is given below each box.

Table 6 Cumulative area fractions for each texture class corresponding to the 10th percentile pesticide reduction efficiency (ΔP) of the whole CDF (all texture classes) for the combination selected for the SWAN-VFSMOD scenarios (Koc 100 L kg⁻¹, duration 8 h, CORINE, variant B)

FOCUS Scenario	10 th percentile ΔP of whole CDF (all texture classes)	HYPRES texture class	sample size N	closest ΔP in CDF of ΔP for texture class			
				ΔP	cumulative area	cumulative area fraction of CDF for texture class	area fraction of whole CDF ³⁾ (all texture classes)
	%			%	ha	ha ha ⁻¹	ha ha ⁻¹
R1	20.625	C	56	53.766	14234.2	0.050 ¹⁾	0.0016
		M	346	23.809	35036.8	0.009	0.0041
		MF	100	20.625	611345.8	0.249 ²⁾	0.0708
		F	178	20.796	62812.1	0.038	0.0073
		VF	11	18.714	233915.7	0.970	0.0271
R2	56.315	C	83	59.363	3210.5	0.007	0.0042
		M	64	56.315	43646.7	0.210	0.0569
		MF	7	44.582	27634.5	1.000	0.0360
		F	18	42.938	5421.3	0.140	0.0071
R3	29.971	C	75	61.776	60.8	0.000	0.0000
		M	225	30.438	31933.9	0.025	0.0143
		MF	27	29.971	160401.3	0.550	0.0718
		F	84	30.071	29395.1	0.083	0.0132
		VF	5	16.629	2627.2	0.130	0.0012
		O	3	27.868	17393.3	0.998	0.0078
R4	44.834	C	93	47.632	1241.0	0.001	0.0001
		M	286	44.834	660297.4	0.086	0.0550
		MF	15	45.493	342763.9	0.471	0.0286
		F	97	43.967	207478.1	0.095	0.0173
		VF	4	62.165	62111.3	0.988	0.0052
		O	3	28.698	96681.6	0.998	0.0081

¹⁾ The binary search algorithm always finds a solution: If ΔP from the 10th percentile profile is below the whole distribution of ΔP for a given texture class (cf. Figure 12), the first row of the CDF (the row with the lowest ΔP) is selected. The determined cumulative area fraction then corresponds to the area fraction of this row. However, the true cumulative area fraction for these cases (highlighted in red) is zero.

²⁾ Cumulative area fractions > 10 % are highlighted in bold.

³⁾ Calculated as the ratio of the value in column “cumulative area” and the total area of the whole CDF (all texture classes). The values in this column should add up to 0.1 for each scenario; however, this is only approximately the case (the sums are between 0.104 for R2 and 0.114 for R4). The reason is that the binary search algorithm does not interpolate, but only finds the ΔP value closest to the target value .

Figure 13 Spatially weighted boxplots of predicted pesticide trapping efficiency (ΔP) according to texture class for all simulated profiles for all scenarios combined (Koc 100 L kg⁻¹, duration 8 h, CORINE, variant B). Boxes: 25th and 75th percentiles, whiskers: min and max. Spatial weighting with area of the scenario/profile combination was applied. Horizontal line: 10th percentile of ΔP of the combined CDF over all scenarios for option CORINE. Texture classes are C = Coarse, M = medium, MF = medium fine, F = fine, VF = very fine, O = organic. The sample size is given below each box.

Table 7 Cumulative area fractions for each texture class corresponding to the 10th percentile pesticide reduction efficiency (ΔP) of the whole pooled CDF (all texture classes and scenarios combined) for the combination selected for the SWAN-VFSMOD scenarios (Koc 100 L kg⁻¹, duration 8 h, CORINE, variant B)

10 th percentile ΔP of whole CDF (all texture classes)	HYPRES texture class	sample size N	closest ΔP in CDF of ΔP for texture class			
			ΔP	cumulative area	cumulative area fraction of CDF for texture class	area fraction of whole CDF ³⁾ (all texture classes)
%			%	ha	ha ha ⁻¹	
26.578	C	307	47.632	1241.0	0.001 ¹⁾	0.000
	F	377	26.700	183889.5	0.043	0.005
	M	921	26.791	67948.7	0.005	0.002
	MF	149	26.578	1914529.5	0.547 ²⁾	0.050
	O	6	27.868	5797.8	0.051	0.000
	VF	20	18.714	237654.7	0.733	0.006

¹⁾ The binary search algorithm always finds a solution: If ΔP from the 10th percentile profile is below the whole distribution of ΔP for a given texture class (cf. Figure 13), the first row of the CDF (the row with the lowest ΔP) is selected. The determined cumulative area fraction then corresponds to the area fraction of this row. However, the true cumulative area fraction for these cases (highlighted in red) is zero.

²⁾ Cumulative area fractions > 10 % are highlighted in **bold**.

³⁾ Calculated as the ratio of the value in column “cumulative area” and the total area of the whole CDF (all texture classes). The values in this column should add up to 0.1; however, the sum is only 0.063. The reason is that the binary search algorithm does not interpolate, but only finds the ΔP value closest to the target value. For class VF the closest value to $\Delta P = 26.578$ % was quite far off (18.714 %).

4 CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

A set of updated VFSSMOD scenarios for FOCUS Step4 simulations has been derived. The new 90th percentile worst case profiles for SWAN-VFSSMOD correspond to the state of the art of VFS modelling and the most recent available soil profile databases and land cover data. The updated SWAN-VFSSMOD scenarios are both more realistic and more conservative than the old scenarios included in SWAN 5.01, and are ready to be integrated in the upcoming version SWAN 5.2.

While the derived SWAN-VFSSMOD scenarios represent the best estimate of a 90th percentile worst case given the available data, this report may also offer a blueprint for revising the scenarios as new data become available.

Potential future updates of the SWAN-VFSSMOD scenarios should include, first of all, a revision of the FOCUS scenario shapefiles because of climate change. For this revision the following changes are suggested:

- 1) the most recent MARS 25 data (i.e., the last 20-30 years) should be used instead of the outdated CRU grid (1961-1990). Consequently, also the weather files for the 10 FOCUS sw scenarios should be updated.
- 2) Moreover, the use of grid-based soil data (SoilGrids; <https://www.isric.org/explore/soilgrids>) instead of using the SGDBE in combination with the SPADE14 and SPADE2 profile databases may be considered. This would make the spatial aggregation of VFSSMOD results much easier, although it would also increase the number of simulations to perform. Of course the number of available soil properties in SoilGrids is not as large as in SPADE14 / SPADE2, but for parameterizing VFSSMOD it would be sufficient.
- 3) Land use may be directly accounted for using CORINE Land Cover instead of using the land use information in the SGDBE.

A scientific publication in a peer-reviewed journal is in preparation.

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6 ANNEX

6.1 Resources

Datasets:

Datasets used in this project are available for download at:

- SGDBE: <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/resource-type/european-soil-database-soil-properties>
- SPADE2: <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/spade-2-soil-profile-analytical-database-europe-version-10>
- SPADE14: <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/spade-14>

Models:

The VFSSMOD version used in this project (v.4.5.2) as well as UH v.3.0.7 are available for download at <https://abe.ufl.edu/faculty/carpena/vfssmod/updates.shtml>

6.2 Spatial extent of the FOCUS R scenarios

Figure A 1 Extent of the FOCUS R1 scenario shapefile (FOCUS, 2001) after intersection with CORINE Land Cover 2018 class 2 (agricultural land)

Figure A 2 Extent of the FOCUS R2 scenario shapefile (FOCUS, 2001) after intersection with CORINE Land Cover 2018 class 2 (agricultural land)

Figure A 3 Extent of the FOCUS R3 scenario shapefile (FOCUS, 2001) after intersection with CORINE Land Cover 2018 class 2 (agricultural land)

Figure A 4 Extent of the FOCUS R4 scenario shapefile (FOCUS, 2001) after intersection with CORINE Land Cover 2018 class 2 (agricultural land)

6.3 Description of tables from SGDBE

The SGDBE is the geometry part of the European Soil Database v2.0 (EC, 2004) and can be obtained here: <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/european-soil-database-v20-vector-and-attribute-data>

Table A 1 Variables contained in stuorg.dbf

variable	description	unit	key or attribute	remarks
SMU	Soil Mapping Unit	n.a.	part of key	
STU	Soil Typological Unit	n.a.	part of key	STUs are not localized within the SMU; SMU and STU have a m:n relationship: a given SMU can have several STUs, and a given STU can occur in several SMUs
PCAREA	area fraction of the SMU covered by the STU	%	attribute	

Table A 2 Variables contained in stu_sgdb.dbf (only the relevant ones are listed)

Variable	description	unit	key or attribute	remarks
STU	Soil Typological Unit	n.a.	key	
USE_DOM	dominant land use in STU	n.a.	attribute	numerical code (Table A 13)
USE_SEC	secondary land use in STU	n.a.	attribute	numerical code (Table A 13)

6.4 Description of SPADE2 tables

SPADE2 consists only of a single table containing profile and horizon data (spade2v11.dbf). Details are given in Hannam et al. (2009). The variables contained in spadev211.dbf are listed in Table A 3.

Table A 3 Variables contained in spadev211.dbf (Hannam et al., 2009)

variable	description	unit	key or attribute	remarks
SMU	Soil Mapping Unit code	n.a.	part of key	
STU	Soil Typological Unit code	n.a.	part of key	
COUNTRY	Country ID	n.a.	part of key	
USE	Land use class associated with profile data	n.a.	part of key	numerical code (Table A 13)
SOIL	Soil name FAO Legend 1974 modified CEC 1985	n.a.	attribute	
PCAREA	area fraction of the SMU covered by the STU	%	attribute	STUarea/SMUarea * 100 %
HORIZON	horizon designation according to FAO Nomenclature	n.a.	part of key	
DEPTH_UP	Upper limit of horizon	cm	attribute	
DEPTH_LO	Lower limit of horizon	cm	attribute	
CLAY	Clay <0.002 mm esd, % oven dry weight (at 105°C)	%	attribute	
SILT	Silt 0.002-0.05 mm esd, % oven dry weight (at 105°C)	%	attribute	
SAND_TOT	Sand 0.05-2 mm esd, % oven dry weight (at 105°C)	%	attribute	
SAND_01	Sand 0.05-0.1 mm esd, % oven dry weight (at 105°C)	%	attribute	
SAND_02	Sand 0.1-0.2 mm esd, % oven dry weight (at 105°C)	%	attribute	
SAND_05	Sand 0.2-0.5 mm esd, % oven dry weight (at 105°C)	%	attribute	
SAND_20	Sand 0.5-2 mm esd, % oven dry weight (at 105°C)	%	attribute	

variable	description	unit	key or attribute	remarks
STONES	Stone content as volume %	%	attribute	
PH_KCL	pH in 0.1 M KCl solution	n.a.	attribute	
PH_KCLSD	standard deviation of pH in KCl	n.a.	attribute	
PH_H2O	pH in H ₂ O solution (soil: water ratio 1:2.5)	n.a.	attribute	
PH_H2OSD	standard deviation of pH in H ₂ O	n.a.	attribute	
PH_CA	pH in 0.01M CaCl ₂ solution	n.a.	attribute	
PH_CASD	Standard Deviation of pH in CaCl ₂	n.a.	attribute	
OC	Organic Carbon content	%	attribute	
OC_SD	Organic Carbon standard deviation	%	attribute	
DB	Bulk Density measured	kg dm ⁻³	attribute	
DB_CALC	Bulk Density calculated	kg dm ⁻³	attribute	
DB_UK_PTF	Bulk density derived from UK pedotransfer function	kg dm ⁻³	attribute	
TEXT1	Dominant surface textural class	n.a.	attribute	
TEXT2	Secondary surface textural class	n.a.	attribute	
WR	Dominant annual average water regime class	n.a.	attribute	
WM1	Water management in agricultural land	n.a.	attribute	
WM2	Purpose of water management system	n.a.	attribute	
WM3	Type of water management system	n.a.	attribute	
SOIL_NEW	New soil type assigned to STU from data provider	n.a.	attribute	
USE_NEW	New land use class assigned to STU from data provider	n.a.	attribute	numerical code (Table A 13)

**Table A 4 Variables contained in cleaned-up profile/horizon table
gethorizons_SPADE2_all_20240304.xlsx**

variable	description	unit	key or attribute	remarks
FOCUS_scen	FOCUS scenario	n.a.	part of key	
maxdepth_cm	maximum depth for averaging ¹⁾ over horizons	cm	attribute	set to 100
ProfileID2	SPADE2 profile ID created by knoell	n.a.	part of key	created as concatenation of STU and USE
FOCUSscen_ProfileID2	concatenation of FOCUS_scen and ProfileID2	n.a.	attribute	
SOIL	Soil name FAO Legend 1974 modified CEC 1985	n.a.	attribute	
USE	Land use class associated with profile data	n.a.	part of key	numerical code (Table A 13)
HORIZON	horizon designation according to FAO Nomenclature	n.a.	part of key	
isRock	binary classifier (1 = is hard rock, 0 = otherwise)	n.a.	attribute	auxiliary variable
startRock	binary classifier (1 = is uppermost hard rock layer; 0 = otherwise)		attribute	auxiliary variable
startdepth_rock	start depth of hard rock	cm	attribute	auxiliary variable
maxdepth_final	final depth for averaging over horizons	cm	attribute	calculated as min (startdepth_rock, 100 cm)
DEPTH_UP	Upper depth of horizon	cm	attribute	
DEPTH_LO	Lower depth of horizon	cm	attribute	
thickness	thickness of horizon	cm	attribute	
min(depth_lo, maxdepth_final)	minimum of DEPTH_LO and maxdepth_final	cm	attribute	auxiliary variable
thickness_above_maxdepth_final	thickness of horizon above maxdepth_final	cm	attribute	weight for weighted averaging
CLAYnorm	normalized clay content		attribute	normalized so that the sum of the three yields 100 %
SILTnorm	normalized silt content		attribute	
SANDnorm	normalized sand content		attribute	
STONES	volumetric stone content	%	attribute	
OC	organic carbon content		attribute	
DB	bulk density measured	kg dm ⁻³	attribute	
DBNEW	final bulk density	kg dm ⁻³	attribute	If DB is present and is NOT flagged as an outlier, DBNEW = DB. If DB is not present, then DBNEW = DBPTF ²⁾ . If DB is present but it is an outlier, than

variable	description	unit	key or attribute	remarks
				DBNEW = DBPTF is used, only if DBPTF is not an outlier; else DBNEW = DB. For all layers where HORIZON starts with R DBNEW was set to 2.4
QA	data quality level		attribute	1 = complete observations and direct application of HYPRES continuous ptf, textural data sum-up to 100% and textural classes meet the data range restriction and observed DB is not an outlier; 2 = same as 1 but textural data were normalized to sum-up to 100%; 3 = same as 1, but missing DB values, HYPRES continuous ptf were applied after DB prediction using the ptf of Hollis et al. (2012); 4 = same as 3, but textural data were normalized to sum up to 100%; 5 = others than {1,...,4, 6, NA}; 6 = rock or organic layer; NA = application of ptf not possible due to data incompleteness
missing_depth_R	checking column		attribute	always FALSE
1) depth-weighted averaging in order to create an effective single-horizon profile for VFSSMOD				
2) DBPTF = bulk density calculated using pedotransfer functions of Hollis et al. (2012)				

6.5 Description of SPADE14 tables

A historic overview on the development of a harmonised soil profile analytical database for Europe is given in Kristensen et al. (2019). Further information on Spade-1.4 are given in Breuning-Madsen and Jones (1995) and Breuning-Madsen et al. (2015). The Spade-1.4 database consists of a directory structure that are named with the 2-letter ISO code for 28 European States. In each directory, two Excel files are present, e.g. XX-EST_HOR.xls and XX-EST_PROF.xls.

All 28 XX-EST_HOR.xls files were row-wisely appended to form one large HOR_all.csv file. The same was done to form one large PROF_all.csv. After that, HOR_all.csv and PROF_all.csv were joined via the unique field PROF_NUM.

SPADE 14 also contains a table linking the profiles to the Soil Typological Units (Links_prof_stu.xlsx). We renamed this table to spade14_stu.xlsx (Table A 5) to avoid confusion with other datasets.

Table A 5 Variables contained in spade14_stu.xlsx

variable	description	unit	key or attribute	remarks
STU_DOM	Soil Typological unit	n.a.	part of key	SPADE14 only contains profiles for dominant STUs (i.e. the STUs covering the largest area fraction in a given SMU)
CNTR_STU	concatenation of country and STU_DOM	n.a.		redundant because country code already contained in PROF_NUM
PROF_NUM	Profile ID	n.a.	part of key	country code + number
country	country code	n.a.		redundant because country code already contained in PROF_NUM

Table A 6 Variables contained in prof_all (Daroussin, 1999)

variable	description	unit	key or attribute	remarks
PROF_NUM	profile id	n.a.	key	
COUNTRY	country code	n.a.	attribute	redundant because country code already contained in PROF_NUM)
SOIL	full 1974 (modified cec 1985) FAO legend soil name	n.a.	attribute	
SOIL90	soil type according to FAO 1990	n.a.	attribute	
TEXT1	dominant surface textural class	n.a.	attribute	
TEXT2	secondary surface textural class	n.a.	attribute	
PM	dominant parent material	n.a.	attribute	semantic description (free text)
SMU	soil mapping unit identifier to which the profile refers (as given by author)	n.a.	attribute	
STU	soil typogical unit identifier to which the profile refers (as given by author)	n.a.	attribute	
LU	dominant land use	n.a.	attribute	semantic description (free text)
GWL_HI	class of mean highest level of a permanent or perched groundwater table	n.a.	attribute	
GWL_LO	class of mean lowest level of a permanent or perched groundwater table	n.a.	attribute	
DR_EFF_A	mean effective root depth for a???	cm	attribute	

variable	description	unit	key or attribute	remarks
DR_EFF_BE	mean effective root depth for beets	cm	attribute	
DR_EFF_CO	mean effective root depth for cotton	cm	attribute	
DR_EFF_MA	mean effective root depth for maize	cm	attribute	
DR_EFF_OL	mean effective root depth for olives	cm	attribute	
DR_EFF_SC	mean effective root depth for spring cereals	cm	attribute	
DR_EFF_SG	mean effective root depth for short grass	cm	attribute	
DR_EFF_WC	mean effective root depth for winter cereals	cm	attribute	
DR_TOT_A	mean total root depth for a???	cm	attribute	
DR_TOT_BE	mean total root depth for beets	cm	attribute	
DR_TOT_CO	mean total root depth for cotton	cm	attribute	
DR_TOT_MA	mean total root depth for maize	cm	attribute	
DR_TOT_OL	mean total root depth for olives	cm	attribute	
DR_TOT_SC	mean total root depth for spring cereals	cm	attribute	
DR_TOT_SG	mean total root depth for short grass	cm	attribute	
DR_TOT_WC	mean total root depth for winter cereals	cm	attribute	
DEPTH_HORO	origin of data for horizons depths	n.a.	attribute	
BD_O	origin of data for bulk density	n.a.	attribute	
BS_O	origin of data for base saturation	n.a.	attribute	
C_N_O	origin of data for carbon/nitrogen ratio	n.a.	attribute	
CACO3_TOTO	origin of data for calcium carbonate equivalent	n.a.	attribute	
CASO4_O	origin of data for gypsum	n.a.	attribute	
CEC_O	origin of data for cation exchange capacity	n.a.	attribute	
EC_O	origin of data for electrical conductivity	n.a.	attribute	
EXCH_CA_O	origin of data for calcium exchangeable base	n.a.	attribute	
EXCH_K_O	origin of data for potassium exchangeable base	n.a.	attribute	
EXCH_MG_O	origin of data for magnesium exchangeable base	n.a.	attribute	
EXCH_NA_O	origin of data for sodium exchangeable base	n.a.	attribute	
EXCH_NA_PO	origin of data for exchangeable sodium percentage of the cec	n.a.	attribute	
GRAVEL_O	origin of data for class percentage of stones and gravel in the soil	n.a.	attribute	
OM_O	origin of data for organic matter content	n.a.	attribute	
PH_O	origin of data for acidity ph	n.a.	attribute	
POR_O	origin of data for total porosity	n.a.	attribute	
STRUCT_O	origin of data for structure type	n.a.	attribute	
TEXT_2_O	origin of data for proportion of particles with size below 2 µm	n.a.	attribute	

variable	description	unit	key or attribute	remarks
TEXT_20_O	origin of data for proportion of particles with size 2-20 µm	n.a.	attribute	
TEXT_50_O	origin of data for proportion of particles with size 20-50 µm	n.a.	attribute	
TEXT_200_O	origin of data for proportion of particles with size 50-200 µm	n.a.	attribute	
TEXT_2000O	origin of data for proportion of particles with size 200-2000 µm	n.a.	attribute	
WC_1_O	origin of data for soil water retention at -1 kpa	n.a.	attribute	
WC_10_O	origin of data for soil water retention at -10 kpa	n.a.	attribute	
WC_100_O	origin of data for soil water retention at -100 kpa	n.a.	attribute	
WC_1500_O	origin of data for soil water retention at -1500 kpa	n.a.	attribute	
WC_FC_O	origin of data for soil water retention at field capacity	n.a.	attribute	
AR_NA_O	origin of data for sodium adsorption ratio	n.a.	attribute	
CACO3_ACTO	origin of data for active calcium carbonate	n.a.	attribute	

Table A 7 Variables contained in hor_all (Daroussin, 1999)

variable	description	unit	key or attribute	remarks
PROF_NUM	profile unique identifier		part of key	
HOR_NUM	horizon sequential number within profile		part of key	
HOR_NAME	horizon name according to the fao system		attribute	
DEPTHSTART	upper limit of horizon	cm	attribute	
DEPTHEND	lower limit of horizon	cm	attribute	
BD	bulk density	g cm ⁻³	attribute	
BS	base saturation	% of CEC	attribute	
C_N	carbon/nitrogen ratio (C/N)	%	attribute	
CACO3_TOT	calcium carbonate equivalent content	%	attribute	gravimetric
CASO4	gypsum content	%	attribute	gravimetric
CEC	cation exchange capacity	cmolc kg ⁻¹	attribute	
EC	class of electrical conductivity	n.a.	attribute	classes correspond to dS m ⁻¹ range at 25 °C

variable	description	unit	key or attribute	remarks
EXCH_CA	calcium exchangeable base	cmolc kg ⁻¹	attribute	
EXCH_K	potassium exchangeable base	cmolc kg ⁻¹	attribute	
EXCH_MG	magnesium exchangeable base	cmolc kg ⁻¹	attribute	
EXCH_NA	sodium exchangeable base	cmolc kg ⁻¹	attribute	
GRAVEL	class of stone and gravel content in the soil		attribute	
OM	organic matter content in organo-mineral layers	%	attribute	gravimetric
PH	pH (in water 1:2.5)		attribute	
POR	total porosity	%	attribute	
STRUCT	structure type		attribute	
TEXT_2	proportion of particles with size below 2 µm	%	attribute	
TEXT_20	proportion of particles with size 2-20 µm	%	attribute	
TEXT_50	proportion of particles with size 20-50 µm	%	attribute	
TEXT_200	proportion of particles with size 50-200 µm	%	attribute	
TEXT_2000	proportion of particles with size 200-2000 µm	%	attribute	
WC_1	soil water content at -1 kPa	%	attribute	pF 1
WC_10	soil water content at -10 kPa	%	attribute	pF 2
WC_100	soil water content at -100 kPa	%	attribute	pF 3
WC_1500	soil water content at -1500 kPa	%	attribute	pF 4.2
WC_FC	soil water content at field capacity	%	attribute	reference soil moisture apparently not harmonized
COUNTRY	country code		attribute	
EXCH_NA_P	exchangeable sodium percentage	% of CEC	attribute	variable names apparently not harmonized
EXCH_NA_PC T			attribute	
EXCH_NA_%			attribute	
AR_NA	sodium adsorption ratio	%	attribute	

**Table A 8 Variables contained in cleaned-up profile/horizon table
 gethorizons_SPADE14_all_20240304.xlsx**

variable	description	unit	key or attribute	remarks
FOCUS_scen	FOCUS scenario	n.a.	part of key	
maxdepth_cm	maximum depth for averaging ¹⁾ over horizons	cm	attribute	set to 100
ProfileID2	SPADE2 profile ID created by knoell	n.a.	part of key	created as concatenation of STU and USE
FOCUSscen_ProfileID2	concatenation of FOCUS_scen and ProfileID2	n.a.	attribute	
SOIL	Soil name FAO Legend 1974 modified CEC 1985	n.a.	attribute	
LUCODE	Land use class associated with profile data	n.a.	part of key	numerical code (Table A 9)
HOR_NUM				
HOR_NAME	horizon designation according to FAO Nomenclature	n.a.	part of key	
isRock	binary classifier (1 = is hard rock, 0 = otherwise)	n.a.	attribute	auxiliary variable
startRock	binary classifier (1 = is uppermost hard rock layer; 0 = otherwise)		attribute	auxiliary variable
startdepth_rock	start depth of hard rock	cm	attribute	auxiliary variable
maxdepth_final	final depth for averaging over horizons	cm	attribute	calculated as min (startdepth_rock, 100 cm)
DEPTHSTART	Upper depth of horizon	cm	attribute	
DEPTHEND	Lower depth of horizon	cm	attribute	
thickness	thickness of horizon	cm	attribute	
min(depth_lo, maxdepth_final)	minimum of DEPTH_LO and maxdepth_final	cm	attribute	auxiliary variable
thickness_above_maxdepth_final	thickness of horizon above maxdepth_final	cm	attribute	weight for weighted averaging

variable	description	unit	key or attribute	remarks
CLAYnorm	normalized clay content		attribute	normalized so that the sum of the three yields 100 %
SILTnorm	normalized silt content		attribute	
SANDnorm	normalized sand content		attribute	
STONE	volumetric stone content	%	attribute	
OC	organic carbon content		attribute	
DB	bulk density measured	kg dm ⁻³	attribute	
DBNEW	final bulk density	kg dm ⁻³	attribute	If DB is present and is NOT flagged as an outlier, DBNEW = DB. If DB is not present, then DBNEW = DBPTF ²⁾ . If DB is present but it is an outlier, then DBNEW = DBPTF is used, only if DBPTF is not an outlier; else DBNEW = DB. For all layers where HORIZON starts with R DBNEW was set to 2.4
QA	data quality level		attribute	1 = complete observations and direct application of HYPRES continuous ptf, textural data sum-up to 100% and textural classes meet the data range restriction and observed DB is not an outlier; 2 = same as 1 but textural data were normalized to sum-up to 100%; 3 = same as 1, but missing DB values, HYPRES continuous ptf were applied after DB prediction using the ptf of Hollis et al. (2012); 4 = same as 3, but textural data were normalized to sum up to 100%; 5 = others than {1,...,4, 6, NA}; 6 = rock or organic layer; NA = application of ptf not possible due to data incompleteness
check_missing_dept_R	checking column		attribute	always FALSE
1) depth-weighted averaging in order to create an effective single-horizon profile for VFSSMOD				
2) DBPTF = bulk density calculated using pedotransfer functions of Hollis et al. (2012)				

6.6 Detailed method to determine number of profile / scenario combinations to be modelled

Processing steps (import_extended.R):

- Read in stu_sgdbe.dbf and stuorg.dbf
- Left Join stuorg and stu_sgdbe via STU → Table Stuorg_stu_sgdbe (stuorg with additional columns USE_DOM and USE_SEC)
- Read in R1234_NUTS_agg_leftjoin_stuorg.xlsx

Processing of SPADE14

- Read in spade14_stu.csv
- COUNTRY <- from CNTR_STU
- Create spade14LU from recodeLUspade14.R and Datei PROF_all.csv
- Left join spade14 and spade14LU via (PROFILE = PROF_NUM) => spade14 with USE
- SPADE1KEY for R1234_NUTS from c("COUNTRY_SPADE14", "STU")
- Left join spade14, R1234_NUTS by c("CNTR_STU" = "SPADE1KEY") => spade1R1234
- Left join stuorg, spade1R1234 by by=c("STU"="STU_DOM") => stuorg_spade14_R1234
- Remove true duplicates

Processing of SPADE2: spade2v11 is a horizon table

- Read in spade2v11.dbf
- PROFILE <= paste(spade2\$STU, spade2\$USE, sep = "_")
- Reduce spade2 to profile-specific data: c("SMU", "STU", "USE", "COUNTRY", "PROFILE", "SRC"), loss of horizon data
- SPADE2KEY for spade from c("SMU", "STU", "COUNTRY")
- SPADE2KEY for R1234_NUTS from c("SMU", "STU", "COUNTRY_SPADE2")
- Left join spade2, R1234_NUTS by c("SPADE2KEY" = "SPADE2KEY") => spade2R1234
- Left join stuorg, spade1R1234 by by=c("STU"="STU") => stuorg_spade2_R1234
- Remove true duplicates
- Same number of columns and column names for stuorg_spade14_R1234 und stuorg_spade2_R1234

#Join both tables and determine unique combinations of R scenario and soil profile

- Append by row stuorg_spade14_R1234 and stuorg_spade2_R1234 to one file --> intermediate table stuorg-stu_sgdbe-spade14-spade2-R1234.xlsx (variables see Table A 9)
- Determine unique combinations of profileID and R scenario in MS Excel → intermediate table combinations_from_shapefile.xlsx containing 3134 combinations of R scenario and soil profile (with SPADE2 profile ID including country code)
- Determine unique combinations of profileID and R scenario in MS Access → intermediate table leftjoin_ProfileID2.xlsx containing 3074 combinations of R scenario and soil profile to be simulated (with SPADE2 profileID NOT including country code)

Table A 9 Columns of table stuorg-stu_sgdbe-spade14-spade2-R1234.xlsx

No.	variable	description	source	value
1	SMU	Soil Mapping Unit	stuorg	
2	STU	Soil Typological Unit	stuorg	
3	PCAREA.x	area percentage of SMU covered by STU	stuorg	
4	USE_DOM	dominant land use of STU	stu_sgdbe	
5	USE_SEC	secondary land use of STU	stu_sgdbe	
6	SRC	source of columns 1-3		„stuorg”
7	USE	land use of soil profile	spade2 or spade14	
8	COUNTRY	country of soil profile		
9	PROFILE	profile ID		
10	SRC.x	source of columns 7-9		„spade14“ or „spade2“
11	SMU.y	Soil Mapping Unit	R1234_NUTS	
12	CNTR_CODE	country code	R1234_NUTS	
13	NUTS_NAME	country name	R1234_NUTS	
14	EU_STAT	EU membership status	R1234_NUTS	“T” or “F”
15	FOCUS_scen	FOCUS scenario	R1234_NUTS	
16	COUNTRY_SPADE14	country code SPADE14	R1234_NUTS	
17	COUNTRY_SPADE2	country code SPADE2	R1234_NUTS	
18	TotalArea_SMU_CNTR_FOCUSscen	Total area of combination SMU / country / FOCUS scenario	R1234_NUTS	
19	stuorg_SMU	Soil Mapping Unit	R1234_NUTS	
20	STU.y	Soil Typological unit	R1234_NUTS	
21	PCAREA.y	area fraction of the SMU that is covered by the STU (%)	R1234_NUTS	
22	SRC.y	source of columns 11-21		“R1234_NUTS” or blank

6.7 Description of spatial aggregation procedure

6.7.1 Spatial input tables

The following tables were used for the creation of spatial cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) (section 6.7.4):

- R1234_grouped_20240411.xlsx (657 records)
- R1234_CORINE_grouped_20240411.xlsx (637 records)

These tables contain the total area of each unique combination of country, FOCUS scenario and Soil Mapping Unit. Variables are given in Table A 10. For the CDF creation .csv versions of these tables were used.

Table A 10 Variables contained in R1234_grouped_20240411.xlsx and R1234_CORINE_grouped_20240411.xlsx

field	description	unit	key or attribute	remarks
CNTR_ID	NUTS country code		part of key	
NAME_ENGL	NUTS country name		attribute	(in national language)
EU_STAT	EU membership status		attribute	T (TRUE) or F (FALSE)
SMU	Soil Mapping Unit		part of key	
FOCUS_scen	FOCUS scenario		part of key	R1, R2, R3 or R4
SumOfShape_Area	area of unique combination of country / SMU / FOCUS scenario	m ²	attribute	

The following tables were used as inputs for calculating the area fractions covered by each soil profile (section 6.7.3):

- R1234_NUTS_agg_leftjoin_stuorg.xlsx (2560 records; variables see Table A 11)
- R1234_NUTS_CLC_agg_leftjoin_stuorg.xlsx (13293 records; variables see Table A 12)

The creation of these two tables is described in section 2.1.

Table A 11 Variables contained in R1234_NUTS_agg_leftjoin_stuorg.xlsx

field	description	unit	remarks
SMU	Soil Mapping Unit		
CNTR_CODE	NUTS country code		
NUTS_NAME	NUTS country name		(in national language)
EU_STAT	EU membership status		T (TRUE) or F (FALSE)
FOCUS_scen	FOCUS scenario		R1, R2, R3 or R4
COUNTRY_SPADE14	country code used in SPADE14		
COUNTRY_SPADE2	country code used in SPADE2		
TotalArea_SMU_CNTR_FOC USscen	area of unique combination of country / SMU / FOCUS scenario	m ²	
stuorg_SMU	SMU from stuorg table		from stuorg.dbf
STU	Soil Typological Unit		from stuorg.dbf
PCAREA	area fraction of the SMU covered by the STU	%	from stuorg.dbf

Table A 12 Variables contained in R1234_NUTS_CLC_agg_leftjoin_stuorg.xlsx

field	description	unit	remarks
SMU	Soil Mapping Unit		
CNTR_CODE	NUTS country code		
NUTS_NAME	NUTS country name		(in national language)
EU_STAT	EU membership status		T (TRUE) or F (FALSE)
Code_18	CORINE Land Cover class		211, 212, 213 etc.
FOCUS_scen	FOCUS scenario		R1, R2, R3 or R4
COUNTRY_SPADE14	country code used in SPADE14		
COUNTRY_SPADE2	country code used in SPADE2		
TotalArea_SMU_CNTR_CLC FOCUSscen	area of unique combination of country / SMU / CLC class / FOCUS scenario	m ²	
stuorg_SMU	SMU from stuorg table		from stuorg.dbf
STU	Soil Typological Unit		from stuorg.dbf
PCAREA	area fraction of the SMU covered by the STU	%	from stuorg.dbf

6.7.2 Recoding of land use for SPADE14

The semantic land use descriptions in the SPADE14 table PROF_all were recoded into Land Use codes according to SPADE2 (Hannam et al. 2009; Table A 13) using R.

Table A 13 Land use codes used in SPADE2 (Hannam et al., 2009)

Land use code	land use description
0	No information
1	Pasture, grassland, grazing land
2	Poplars
3	Arable land, cereals
4	Wasteland, shrub
5	Forest, coppice
6	Horticulture
7	Vineyards
8	Garrigue
9	Bush, macchia
10	Moor
11	Halophile grassland
12	Arboriculture, orchard
13	Industrial crops
14	Rice
15	Cotton
16	Vegetables
17	Olive trees
18	Recreation
19	Extensive pasture, grazing, rough pasture
20	Dehesa (extensive pastoral system in forest parks in Spain)
21	Cultivos enarenados (artificial soils for orchards in SE Spain)
22	Wildlife refuge, land above timberline

The classification of the verbatim SPADE14 land use descriptions into SPADE2 numeric land use codes was done sequentially. First, the verbatim SPADE14 land use descriptions were set to lower case in order to ease the matching with regular expressions. Subsequently, a series of rules (Table A 14) was applied sequentially to the land use descriptions using regular expressions. The code is available in the digital annex (recodeLUspade14.R).

Table A 14 Classification rules applied to SPADE14 land use descriptions

Step	Pattern in SPADE14 land use description	Attributed SPADE2 LU Code
1	Contains "olive"	7
2	Contains "rice"	14
3	Contains "cotton"	15
4	Contains "olive"	7
5	Whole and only word "orchard"	12
6	Contains "grass", "graz", "pasture", "meadow" or "heath" AND does NOT contain "forest" or "arable" or starts with "agric" or starts with "bush"	1
6.a	Must contain SPADE2 LU Code 1 from step 6 AND contain "exten", "rough" or "natural"	19
6.b	Must contain SPADE2 LU Code 1 from step 6 AND contain "halophile"	11
7	Contains "marsh"	11
8	Starts with "arable" or contains "cereals" or "crop" AND does not contain "forest"	3
9	Contains "bush", "wast", "shrub", "schrub", "scrub", or "layland" or starts with "non"	4
9.a.	Must contain SPADE2 LU Code 5 from step 9 AND contain "recreat"	18
10.	Contains "recreat"	18
11.	Contains "forest", "pinus" or "wood" AND does not contain "arable", "agric", "grass", "cereals", "wild"	5
12	Contains "vegetab"	16
13	Contains "horti"	6
14	Contains "moor", "swamp" or "peat"	10
15	Contains "wildlife"	22
16	Contains "garrigue"	8
17 ¹⁾	Starts with "agric", "arable", "cereals" or "field"	3
18 ¹⁾	Starts with "orchard"	12
19 ¹⁾	Starts with "forest"	5
20 ¹⁾	Starts with "grass"	1
21	All remaining after step 20	0

¹⁾ Steps 17-20 address mixed land use classes in SPADE14 such as e.g. "grassland / arable land". It is assumed that the first term is the dominant land use of the corresponding spatial unit.

6.7.3 Calculation of area fractions for the different profiles

This is a documentation of the final version of the script (import_extended.R).

- 1) set flag isCLC (TRUE or FALSE)
- 2) Read in input tables from SGDBE: stu_sgdb.dbf, stuorg.dbf
- 3) stuorg: scale sum to STU shares to 100 % for each SMU
- 4) add dominant and secondary land use types per STU to stuorg (left join of stu_sgdb to stuorg)
- 5) Replace USE_DOM = 0 and USE_SEC = 0 with NA
- 6) import SPADE2 database;
- 7) import SPADE14 table linking STUs to profiles (spade14_stu.csv); create country code (first two characters of profileID)
- 8) import table with polygon areas as "R1234_NUTS"
R1234_NUTS_CLC_agg_leftjoin_stuorg.xlsx (for case "isCLC = TRUE")
R1234_NUTS_agg_leftjoin_stuorg.xlsx (for case "isCLC = FALSE")
- 9) import table with recoded land uses for SPADE14: join land use code to SPADE14 via ProfileID
- 10) SPADE14: generate combined field STU_PROFID
- 11) add a field SRC (source) to spade14, spade2, stuorg and R1234_NUTS tables for later identification of columns
- 12) R1234_NUTS: Create columns SPADE1KEY and SPADE2KEY to enable join with spade14 and spade2 tables
- 13) left join of R1234_NUTS to spade14 → table spade1R1234_STUCNTR
- 14) left join of spade1R1234_STUCNTR to stuorg; select only unique combinations → table stuorg_spade14_R1234
- 15) SPADE2: apply updated land use (in additional column USE_NEW) to column USE where available; Replace -9999 values (No data) in column USE with 0
- 16) SPADE2: create ProfileID as concatenation of STU and USE
- 17) SPADE2: Select only unique combinations of "SMU", "STU", "USE", "COUNTRY", "PROFILE", "SRC")
- 18) SPADE2 create column SPADE2KEY as concatenation of SMU, STU and country
- 19) left joint of R1234 to spade2; select only unique combinations → table spade2R1234
- 20) select only complete cases of stuorg_spade14_R1234 and stuorg_spade2_R1234
- 21) Remove columns not needed anymore from stuorg_spade14_R1234 and stuorg_spade2_R1234
- 22) check identity of field names of both tables; order columns so that both tables have the same order; append stuorg_spade14_R1234 and stuorg_spade2_R1234 → table "link"; save as tuorg-stu_sgdb-spade14-spade2-R1234.xlsx
- 23) link: set all remaining NA values in USE_DOM and USE_SEC to 0
- 24) link: add area percentage covered by dominant land use (USE_DOM_PERC_AREA):
IF there is no secondary land use, set percentage to 80
ELSE IF no dominant land use either: set percentage to NA
ELSE (secondary land use present): set percentage to 60
- 25) link: add area percentage covered by secondary land use (USE_SEC_PERC_AREA):
IF there is no secondary land use, set percentage to NA
ELSE (secondary land use present): set percentage to 30
- 26) link: add area percentage of actual land use of soil profile (USE_PERC_AREA)
IF USE = USE_DOM and USE_DOM > 0, set percentage to USE_DOM_PERC_AREA
ELSE IF = USE_SEC and USE_SEC > 0, set percentage to USE_SEC_PERC_AREA
ELSE (use corresponds neither to dominant nor to secondary land use), set percentage to 10
- 27) link: some consistency checks; remove STUs without valid profiles
- 28) link: add new field as concatenation of SMU and STU

- 29) link: calculate profile area fractions (PROFILE_PERC_AREA) for each SMU_STU (a SMU / STU combination can have more than one profile, and they can have different or the same land use); the fact that due to the columns FOCUS_scen, country (for SPADE2) and
- 30) CODE_18 (for option CORINE) there are multiple records with the same SMU / STU / profile combination is also dealt with here so that the sums of the area fractions are correct
- 31) link: check whether sum of PROFILE_PERC_AREA for each SMU_STU combination is <= 100
- 32) link: calculate variable “fractions” as
$$\text{fractions} = \text{STUSHARE} / 100 * \text{PROFILE_PERC_AREA} / 100$$
; export table link.csv for CDF generation (with prefix CLC_ or noCLC_)
- 33) calculate final area fraction of SMU covered by a given profile; export results as smu_prof_fracs_tpt.csv (with prefix CLC_ or noCLC_) for quality assurance

Table A 15 Variables contained in of CLC_link_table.csv or noCLC_link_table.csv

No.	field	description	unit	remarks
1	SMU	Soil Mapping Unit		
2	STU	Soil Typological Unit		
3	STUSHARE	area percentage of SMU covered by STU	%	
4	USE_DOM	area percentage of SMU covered by STU		
5	USE_SEC	dominant land use of STU		
6	SRC	secondary land use of STU		
7	USE	source of columns 1-3		
8	COUNTRY	land use of soil profile		
9	PROFILE	profile ID		
10	SRC.x	source of columns 7-9		„spade14“ or „spade2“
11	SMU.y	Soil Mapping Unit		
12	CNTR_CODE	country code		
13	NUTS_NAME	country name		
14	EU_STAT	EU membership status		
15	Code_18	code of CORINE Land Cover class (e.g. 211)		only in CLC_link_table.csv
16	FOCUS_scen	FOCUS scenario		
17	COUNTRY_SPADE14	country code SPADE14		
18	COUNTRY_SPADE2	country code SPADE2		
19	TotalArea_SMU_CNTR_CLC_FOCUSScen	Total area of combination SMU / country / FOCUS scenario	m ²	
20	stuorg_SMU	Soil Mapping Unit		
21	STU.y	Soil Typological unit		
22	PCAREA	area fraction of SMU covered by STU	%	
23	SRC.y	source of columns 11-22		
24	USE_DOM_PERC_AREA	area fraction of SMU/STU combination covered by dominant land use	%	
25	USE_SEC_PERC_AREA	area fraction of SMU/STU combination covered by secondary land use	%	
26	USE_PERC_AREA	area fraction of SMU/STU combination covered by the current land use (field USE)	%	
27	SMUSTU	Concatenated string of SMU and STU		
28	PROFILE_PERC_AREA	area fraction of SMU/STU combination covered by the current soil profile	%	
29	fractions	area fraction of SMU covered by the current soil profile	m ² m ⁻²	
30	SMUPROFILE	Concatenated string of SMU and PROFILE		

6.7.4 Calculation of spatial CDFs

Spatial cumulative distribution functions of the target VFSSMOD output variable ΔP (relative reduction of incoming pesticide load by the VFS) were calculated in R. The script createSpatialCDF.R can be found in the digital annex.

Input tables:

- Table of area fractions covered by the different profiles: CLC_link_table.csv or noCLC_link_table.csv (see Table A 15)
- VFSSMOD results: R1234_30mm_noWT_out_20240526.xlsx (Variant A) or R1234_30mm_noWT_out_20240610.xlsx (Variant B) (see Table A 16)
- Table with areas of unique combination of country / SMU / FOCUS scenario: R1234_CORINE_grouped_20240411.csv or R1234_grouped_20240411_ohne_CNT_NAMES.csv (.csv versions of the Excel files documented in Table A 10)

Output:

- One CSV file per combination of FOCUS scenarios (R1, R2, ..., R4), CORINE or non-CORINE, KOC, DUR and timestep (e.g. R1_KOC100_DUR1_TS15.csv, see Table A 19)
- One plot per above mentioned combination with x = ΔP (%) and y = cumulative area percentage (%)
- One single file *_sourceForCumArea.calc.csv for QA reasons.

The workflow in createSpatialCDF.R was as follows:

- 1) set flag is.CORINE (TRUE or FALSE)
- 2) import table with area fractions (CLC_link_table.csv or noCLC_link_table.csv) as "link"
- 3) import VFSSMOD results as "vsmodOutput"
- 4) import table with areas of country / SMU / scenario combinations (R1234_CORINE_grouped_20240411.csv or R1234_grouped_20240411_ohne_CNT_NAMES.csv) as "smuAreas"
- 5) From table link, calculate total area fractions of a given profile per SMU (by summing up); export to intermediate data frame totalAreaFracPerSMU (Table A 17)
- 6) table smuAreas: remove UK and other non-EU member states
- 7) table smuAreas: sum up areas for each combination of SMU and FOCUS_scen → new table sumAreasNew
- 8) join total area fractions (table totalAreaFracPerSMU) with VFSSMOD output (table vsmodOutput) via field PROFILE
- 9) join the resulting table with table sumAreasNew via field SMUSCEN → table z
- 10) table z: remove invalid records
- 11) create field ID (concatentation of FOCUS scenario, CORINE or non-CORINE, Koc, duration and timestep)
- 12) Calculate CDFs using a loop over the unique values of ID; write a .csv file and create a plot for each CDF
- 13) Write table z as *_sourceForCumArea.calc.csv for quality assurance

Table A 16 Variables contained in VFSMOD result tables R1234_30mm_noWT_out_20240526.xlsx (Variant A) and R1234_30mm_noWT_out_20240610.xlsx (Variant B).

field	description	unit	remarks
Filename	Name of output file before merging	n.a.	
Koc_L_kg	linear sorption coefficient normalized to organic carbon (Koc)	L kg ⁻¹	
timestep_irn_iro_min	time step of runoff and rainfall hydrographs	min	value always 15
Project	concatenation of FOCUS scenario, rainfall volume and event duration		e.g. R1_30_1h
FOCUS_scenario	FOCUS scenario		
duration_h	duration of rainfall event	h	1 or 8
Profile_ID	soil profile ID		
deltaQ_perc	relative reduction of total inflow (runoff + rainfall)	%	
deltaE_perc	relative reduction of eroded sediment load	%	
deltaR_perc	relative reduction of incoming runoff volume	%	
deltaP_perc	relative reduction of incoming pesticide load	%	
Vi_m3	surface runoff inflow into the VFS	m ³	
Ei_kg	incoming eroded sediment load	kg	
Fph	phase distribution coefficient	pH	
Pesticide_input_mi_mg	pesticide input into the VFS	mg	absolute masses
Pesticide_output_mo_mg	pesticide outflow from the VFS		
mf_sed_mg	pesticide trapped with sediment		
mfml_mg	pesticide trapped in mixing layer		
mresn_mg	pesticide residue remobilization at next event		
Source_Area_m2	source area of incoming runoff, eroded sediment and pesticides	m ²	
mi_mg_m2	pesticide input into the VFS	mg m ⁻²	masses normalized to source area
mo_mg_m2	pesticide outflow from the VFS		
mop_mg_m2	particle-bound pesticide outflow		
mod_mg_m2	dissolved pesticide outflow		
mf_mg_m2	pesticide trapped in VFS		
mfsed_mg_m2	pesticide trapped with sediment		
mfml_mg_m2	pesticide trapped in mixing layer		
mfml0_mg_m2	pesticide in mixing layer from last event		
mres1_mg_m2	Total surface residue (mres1 = mfml + mfsed + mfml0)		
Tot_res_after_deg_mg_m2	Total residue after degradation (here: 1 d)		
Dissolved_surf_res_	Dissolved surface residue after degradation		

field	description	unit	remarks
after_deg_mg_m2			
Sorbed_surf_res_after_deg_mg_m2	Sorbed surface residue after degradation		
mresn_mg_m2	pesticide residue remobilization at next event		
d50_cm	median particle diameter (calculated internally in VFSSMOD)	cm	
Runtime_s	simulation run time	s	

Table A 17 Variables contained in intermediate data frame totalAreaFracPerSMU

field	description	unit	remarks
SMUPROFILE	concatenation of SMU and PROFILE	n.a.	
SMU	Soil Mapping Unit	n.a.	
PROFILE	Profile ID	n.a.	
FRACTION	Total area fraction of the SMU covered by the profile	m ² m ⁻²	

Table A 18 Variables contained in intermediate data frame smuAreasNew

field	description	unit	remarks
SMUSCEN	SMU / scenario combination		Concatenated string of SMU and FOCUS scenario
SumOfShapeArea	total area covered by the SMU / scenario combination	m ²	

Table A 19 Variables contained in output CDF files (.csv)

field	description	unit	remarks
ID	Combined string of FOCUS Scenario, (CORINE), KOC, duration and timestep	n.a.	same value for all rows of the file
Project	concatenation of FOCUS scenario, rainfall volume and duration	n.a.	same value for all rows of the file
filename	name of the file with VFSSMOD results	n.a.	same value for all rows of the file
SMU	Soil mapping unit	n.a.	
Profile_ID	soil profile ID	n.a.	
ProfileArea	Area covered by the SMU / profile combination	ha	calculated as FRACTION * SumOfShapeArea / 10000
deltaP_perc	relative reduction of incoming pesticide load by the VFS	%	sorted in ascending order; x axis of the CDF
CumAreaPerc	Cumulative area percentage	%	y axis of the CDF

6.7.5 Determine 90th percentile worst case profile from CDF

An R script was developed to identify, from a given CDF, the profile that corresponds to the 10th spatial percentile of ΔP . The script profileID_90th_PPerc.R can be found in the digital annex (see section 6.11).

Input

- Spatial CDFs of ΔP in .csv format (fields see Table A 19)

Output

- 90thPercentileData_R1234_profile_in.csv

The field names of the output file are the same as in Table A 19, but the file contains only one record per CDF.

The workflow in the script is as follows:

- 1) Implement a binary search algorithm
- 2) Run a loop over all CDFs; from each CDF, extract the record with the cumulative area percentage (CumAreaPerc) closest to 10
- 3) Write all extracted records to .csv file

An overview of the extracted 90th percentile worst case profiles is given in Table A 20.

Table A 20 Extracted 90th percentile worst case profiles for all CDFs

infiltration variant	scenario	Land Cover option	Koc (L kg ⁻¹)	event duration	SMU	Profile ID	Profile Area (ha)	ΔP (%)	cumul. area percentage (%)
B	R1	CORINE	100	1	490034	DE40	184459.3	9.145	10.539
B	R1	CORINE	100	8	337242	FR27	24958.7	20.625	9.989
B	R1	CORINE	10000	1	490034	DE40	184459.3	68.776	10.539
B	R1	CORINE	10000	8	337242	FR27	24958.7	74.263	9.989
B	R1	noCORINE	100	1	490034	DE40	270768.8	9.145	10.106
B	R1	noCORINE	100	8	490041	490150_3	84268.2	20.796	10.248
B	R1	noCORINE	10000	1	490034	DE40	270768.8	68.776	10.106
B	R1	noCORINE	10000	8	490041	490150_3	84268.2	74.313	10.248
B	R2	CORINE	100	1	3510385	PT22	2877.1	21.966	10.049
B	R2	CORINE	100	8	330175	330549_1	3140.4	56.315	10.001
B	R2	CORINE	10000	1	3510385	PT22	2877.1	79.065	10.049
B	R2	CORINE	10000	8	330175	330549_1	3140.4	90.029	10.001
B	R2	noCORINE	100	1	330665	332410_1	7080.3	23.925	10.025
B	R2	noCORINE	100	8	330665	332410_1	7080.3	77.681	10.025
B	R2	noCORINE	10000	1	330665	332410_1	7080.3	79.552	10.025
B	R2	noCORINE	10000	8	330665	332410_1	7080.3	94.818	10.025
B	R3	CORINE	100	1	390272	390906_5	57943.4	11.562	10.218
B	R3	CORINE	100	8	330180	330562_1	34484.2	29.971	10.380

infiltration variant	scenario	Land Cover option	Koc (L kg ⁻¹)	event duration	SMU	Profile ID	Profile Area (ha)	ΔP (%)	cumul. area percentage (%)
B	R3	CORINE	10000	1	390272	390906_5	57943.4	69.721	10.218
B	R3	CORINE	10000	8	330180	330562_1	34484.2	77.941	10.380
B	R3	noCORINE	100	1	3860006	SI6	117.2	11.802	9.889
B	R3	noCORINE	100	8	3860006	SI17	1054.9	30.783	9.757
B	R3	noCORINE	10000	1	3860006	SI6	117.2	69.795	9.889
B	R3	noCORINE	10000	8	3860006	SI17	1054.9	78.179	9.757
B	R4	CORINE	100	1	340234	ES29	330063.1	12.747	9.884
B	R4	CORINE	100	8	340234	ES29	330063.1	44.834	9.876
B	R4	CORINE	10000	1	340234	ES29	330063.1	52.117	9.884
B	R4	CORINE	10000	8	340234	ES29	330063.1	70.821	9.876
B	R4	noCORINE	100	1	340234	ES29	499176.3	12.747	9.927
B	R4	noCORINE	100	8	340234	ES29	499176.3	44.834	10.151
B	R4	noCORINE	10000	1	340234	ES29	499176.3	52.117	9.927
B	R4	noCORINE	10000	8	340234	ES29	499176.3	70.821	10.151
A	R1	CORINE	100	1	490032	490120_3	53206.1	9.140	9.942
A	R1	CORINE	100	8	330132	330433_3	55928.6	19.523	9.744
A	R1	CORINE	10000	1	490032	490120_3	53206.1	68.774	9.942
A	R1	CORINE	10000	8	330132	330433_5	55928.6	74.176	9.778
A	R1	noCORINE	100	1	490032	490120_3	70618.9	9.140	9.931
A	R1	noCORINE	100	8	330132	330433_3	69959.3	19.523	9.889
A	R1	noCORINE	10000	1	490032	490120_3	70618.9	68.774	9.931
A	R1	noCORINE	10000	8	330132	330433_5	69959.3	74.176	9.967
A	R2	CORINE	100	1	3510387	PT2	24853.9	19.753	9.710
A	R2	CORINE	100	8	390276	390922_7	1540.5	45.933	10.031
A	R2	CORINE	10000	1	3510387	PT2	24853.9	78.512	9.691
A	R2	CORINE	10000	8	3860048	SI6	47.6	87.434	9.830
A	R2	noCORINE	100	1	300003	GR3	12590.7	23.804	9.851
A	R2	noCORINE	100	8	3510387	PT2	72943.3	46.870	11.337
A	R2	noCORINE	10000	1	300003	GR3	12590.7	79.523	9.851
A	R2	noCORINE	10000	8	3510387	PT2	72943.3	87.922	11.337
A	R3	CORINE	100	1	330689	FR111	34137.2	9.369	9.768
A	R3	CORINE	100	8	430006	AT8	4.7	17.351	9.995
A	R3	CORINE	10000	1	330689	FR111	34137.2	69.041	9.768
A	R3	CORINE	10000	8	330679	332449_1	4913.3	73.245	9.976
A	R3	noCORINE	100	1	390272	390905_5	218279.1	7.963	10.074
A	R3	noCORINE	100	8	390272	390905_5	218279.1	7.591	9.777

infiltration variant	scenario	Land Cover option	Koc (L kg ⁻¹)	event duration	SMU	Profile ID	Profile Area (ha)	ΔP (%)	cumul. area percentage (%)
A	R3	noCORINE	10000	1	390272	390905_5	218279.1	68.636	10.074
A	R3	noCORINE	10000	8	390272	390905_5	218279.1	68.979	9.777
A	R4	CORINE	100	1	390272	390906_3	52912.3	11.950	10.171
A	R4	CORINE	100	8	3510396	3511358_5	575.4	16.300	9.948
A	R4	CORINE	10000	1	390272	390906_3	52912.3	51.668	10.171
A	R4	CORINE	10000	8	3510396	3511358_5	575.4	55.805	9.948
A	R4	noCORINE	100	1	3860006	SI6	117.2	9.888	9.927
A	R4	noCORINE	100	8	390278	390929_6	9521.1	13.474	9.901
A	R4	noCORINE	10000	1	3860006	SI6	117.2	50.589	9.927
A	R4	noCORINE	10000	8	390278	390929_6	9521.1	54.316	9.901

6.8 Complete VFSSMOD parameterization

A complete set of VFSSMOD inputs can be found in the following files in the digital annex (for Koc = 100 L kg⁻¹):

- Variant A: R1234_30mm_Koc100_15min_20240526.csv
- Variant B: R1234_30mm_Koc100_15min_20240610.csv

The input files for Koc = 10000 L kg⁻¹ are identical except for the Koc.

6.9 Manning's roughness coefficient for VFS (RNA)

The VFSSMOD manual (Muñoz-Carpena and Parsons, 2022) contains an overview table of the values most commonly used in overland flow routing (according to Engman, 1986). The VFSSMOD parameterization guidance (Ritter et al., 2023) recommends a default value of RNA = 0.45 (grass (blue grass sod), well-maintained, good and dense stand). A Sensitivity analysis (Muñoz-Carpena et al., 1999) showed that for RNA values > 0.3 filter strip performance was not sensitive to the value of RNA. For consistency we suggest using 0.4 as in Brown et al. (2012).

From a regulatory perspective, perhaps the assumption of a well maintained VFS might be questionable, depending on what the average (worst-case?) farmer might do in the field. We could of course consider other levels like degraded (not well maintained) vegetation, but this could create inconsistency with FOCUS step3 (note that the CN and MUSS parameterization in FOCUS PRZM also assume “good condition”).

Cover	Manning's n range (recommended) $\text{ms}^{-1/3}$
Bare sand	0.01-0.013 (0.011)
Bare clay-loam (eroded)	0.012-0.033 (0.02)
Fallow - no residue)	0.006-0.16 (0.05)
Range (natural)	0.01-0.32 (0.13)
Range (clipped)	0.02-0.24 (0.10)
Grass (bluegrass sod)	0.39-0.63 (0.45)
Short grass prairie	0.10-0.20 (0.15)
Dense grass ^a	0.17-0.30 (0.24)
Bermuda grass	0.30-0.48 (0.41)

^aWeeping lovegrass, bluegrass, buffalo grass, blue gramm grass, native grass mix (OK), alfalfa, lespedeza

Figure A 5 Tabulated values of Manning's n for different vegetation types and bare surfaces. Source: Muñoz-Carpena and Parsons (2022)

6.10 Confusion matrix for predicting missing profile texture using the dominant topsoil texture class of the STU

(Some explanations how to interpret a confusion matrix can be found here: <https://www.v7labs.com/blog/confusion-matrix-guide>)

The confusion matrix for all occurring combinations of soil profile with texture information and STU (n = 1233) is shown in Figure A 6. Note that the same profile can occur in several STUs.

Figure A 6 Confusion matrix for all combinations of profiles with texture information and STU (n = 1233)

6.11 List of delivered files (digital annex)

List of delivered files (120333_digital_annex_20250319.zip; sent via Cryptshare on 19/03/2025):

Folder 0_Geodata contains all spatial data:

- Subfolder Processed_FOCUS_scenario_shapefiles:
 - Subfolder FOCUS_NUTS: FOCUS R scenario shapefiles after intersection with NUTS (see section 2.1)
 - Subfolder FOCUS_NUTS_CLC2018: FOCUS R scenario shapefiles after intersection with NUTS and CORINE Land Cover 2018 class 2 (see section 2.1)
- Subfolder SGDBE:
 - stuorg.dbf (see section 2.1; Table A 1)
 - stu_sgdbe.dbf ((see section 2.1; Table A 2)
- Subfolder Spatial_tables:
 - Subfolder Area_fractions
 - CLC_link_table.csv (see sections 2.3.1, 6.7.3; Table A 15)
 - noCLC_link_table.csv (see sections 2.3.1, 6.7.3; ; Table A 15)
 - CLC_smu_prof_fracs_tpt.csv (see section 6.7.3)
 - noCLC_smu_prof_fracs_tpt.csv (see section 6.7.3)
 - Subfolder Spatial_input_tables
 - R1234_grouped_20240411.xlsx (657 records) (see sections 2.1, 6.7.1; Table A 10)
 - R1234_CORINE_grouped_20240411.xlsx (637 records) (see sections 2.1, 6.7.1; Table A 10)
 - R1234_NUTS_agg_leftjoin_stuorg.xlsx (see sections 2.1, 6.6, 6.7.1, 6.7.3; Table A 11)
 - R1234_NUTS_CLC_agg_leftjoin_stuorg.xlsx (see sections 2.1, 6.7.1, 6.7.3; Table A 12)
 - Intermediate_tables
 - stuorg-stu_sgdbe-spade14-spade2-R1234.xlsx (see sections 2.1, 6.6)
 - combinations_from_shapefile (3134 records; see section 6.6)
 - leftjoin_ProfileID2 (3074 records; see section 6.6)

Folder 1_Soil_profile_data contains all soil profile/horizon data:

- Subfolder SPADE14
 - spade14_stu.csv / .xlsx
 - PROF_all.csv
 - HOR_all.csv
- Subfolder SPADE2
 - spadev211.dbf
- Subfolder processed_horizon_data
 - gethorizons_SPADE14_all_20240304.xlsx (see sections 2.2.1, Table A 8)
 - gethorizons_SPADE2_all_20240304.xlsx (see sections 2.2.1, Table A 4)
 - spade2_DBNPTF_VGM_parms_2024-01-26_14-17-31.xlsx (see section 6.10; used by confusionMatrix.R)
 - spade14_DBNPTF_VGM_parms_2024-01-30_13-05-28.xlsx (see section 6.10; used by confusionMatrix.R)
- Subfolder effective_single_horizon_profiles:
 - 2024_effectiveSingleHoriz_20240305b_SAV_20240504b.xlsx: final scenario / profile combinations for modelling with VFSMOD (1897 records; see section 2.2.1)

- profileHorizonsMissingValues_20240305.xlsx: List of eliminated scenario / profile combinations due to missing data (1104 records; see section 2.2.1)
- effectiveSingleHoriz.xlsx: plain table with scenario / profile combinations (1970 records, since very shallow profiles have not been removed yet; used as input by confusionMatrix.R (see section 6.10))

Folder 2_UH contains all UH inputs and outputs (see section 2.2.4):

- Subfolder 15_min (15 min = selected time step for output hydrographs)
 - Subfolder inputs: 8 UH input files (.inp)
 - Subfolder output: output files for 8 simulations
 - rainfall hydrographs (.irn)
 - runoff hydrographs (.iro)
 - output file hydrograph calculation (.out)
 - output file erosion calculation (.hyt)
 - sediment properties input file for VFSSMOD (.isd); from this file only the variable CI (eroded sediment concentration in runoff) was used further
 - irn_to_csv_15min.csv: reformatted rainfall hydrographs (1 row = 1 UH run)
 - iro_to_csv_15min.csv: reformatted runoff hydrographs (1 row = 1 UH run)

Folder 3_VFSSMOD contains all VFSSMOD inputs and outputs (see section 2.2.4):

- R1234_30mm_Koc100_15min_20240526.csv: complete VFSSMOD inputs for variant A
- R1234_30mm_Koc100_15min_20240610.csv: complete VFSSMOD inputs for variant B
- R1234_30mm_noWT_out_20240526.xlsx: complete VFSSMOD outputs (.owq file) for variant A
- R1234_30mm_noWT_out_20240610.xlsx: complete VFSSMOD outputs (.owq file) for variant B
- 120333_raw_VFSSMOD_inputs_outputs_20240526.7z: complete VFSSMOD input and output files for all simulations, variant A
- 120333_raw_VFSSMOD_inputs_outputs_20240610.7z: complete VFSSMOD input and output files for all simulations, variant B

Folder 4_CDFs contains all spatial CDFs of ΔP that have been created (see sections 2.3.2, 3.2, 6.7.4)

- Subfolder variant_A (profiles with hard rock in < 100 cm depth were simulated with the shallow water table option)
 - Subfolder CDFs (66 files)
 - 32 CDFs as graph (.png)
 - 32 CDFs as table (.csv)
 - sourceForCumAreacalc_variantA.csv (for quality assurance; see section 6.7.4)
 - CORINEsourceForCumAreaCalc_variantA.csv (for quality assurance; see section 6.7.4)
 - Subfolder 10th_perc_profiles:
 - R1234_90th_perc_profiles_with_VFSSMOD_params_20240527.xlsx
 - Subfolder pooled_CDFs:
 - 8 pooled CDFs (over all 4 R scenarios) as table (.xlsx) (see section 3.5)
- Subfolder variant_B (all profiles were simulated with classical Green-Ampt infiltration)
 - Subfolder CDFs (66 files)
 - 32 CDFs as graph (.png)
 - 32 CDFs as table (.csv)
 - sourceForCumAreacalc_variantB.csv (for quality assurance; see section 6.7.4)
 - CORINEsourceForCumAreaCalc_variantB.csv (for quality assurance; see section 6.7.4)
 - Subfolder 10th_perc_profiles:
 - R1234_90th_perc_profiles_with_VFSSMOD_params_noWT_20240610.xlsx
 - Subfolder pooled_CDFs
 - 8 pooled CDFs (over all 4 R scenarios) as table (.xlsx) (see section 3.5)

Folder 5_Boxplots contains spatially weighted boxplots comparing the descriptive statistics of ΔP for the different SGDBE texture classes with ΔP of the 90th percentile worst-case profiles ... (see sections 2.5, 3.5)

- Subfolder wtd_boxplots_2024-12-11-b
 - Subfolder variant_A: 1 boxplot for each combination of scenario, Koc, duration and CORINE / no CORINE (32 files)
 - Subfolder varA_xlsx_full: full CDFs for each texture class (1 .csv file per combination of scenario, Koc, duration and CORINE / no CORINE)
 - Subfolder varA_xlsx_short: 10th percentile profiles for each texture class (1 .csv file per combination of scenario, Koc, duration and CORINE / no CORINE)
 - Subfolder variant_B: 1 boxplot for each combination of scenario, Koc, duration and CORINE / no CORINE (32 files)
 - Subfolder varB_xlsx_full: full CDFs for each texture class (1 .csv file per combination of scenario, Koc, duration and CORINE / no CORINE)
 - Subfolder varB_xlsx_short: 10th percentile profiles for each texture class (1 .csv file per combination of scenario, Koc, duration and CORINE / no CORINE)
- Subfolder wtd_boxplots_2024-12-12_pooled
 - Subfolder variant_A: 1 pooled boxplot (over all scenarios) for each combination of Koc, duration and CORINE / no CORINE (8 files)
 - Subfolder varA_xlsx_full: full CDFs for each texture class (1 .csv file per combination of Koc, duration and CORINE / no CORINE)
 - Subfolder varA_xlsx_short: 10th percentile profiles for each texture class (1 .csv file per combination of Koc, duration and CORINE / no CORINE)
 - Subfolder variant_B: 1 pooled boxplot (over all scenarios) for each combination of Koc, duration and CORINE / no CORINE (8 files)
 - Subfolder varB_xlsx_full: full CDFs for each texture class (1 .csv file per combination of Koc, duration and CORINE / no CORINE)
 - Subfolder varB_xlsx_short: 10th percentile profiles for each texture class (1 .csv file per combination of Koc, duration and CORINE / no CORINE)

Folder 6_Comparison_with_previous_SWAN-VFSMOD_scenarios (see sections 2.4, 3.4)

- Subfolder test_simulations_vfsm_v424: contains the 16 test simulations with the old VFSMOD executable vfsm v.4.2.4 included in the portable version of SWAN 5
 - Subfolder Koc100: contains all VFSMOD input and output files for Koc 100 L kg⁻¹
 - Subfolder Koc10000: contains all VFSMOD input and output files for Koc 10000 L kg⁻¹
 - merged_owq_Koc100.xlsx: summary table of VFSMOD results for Koc 100 L kg⁻¹
 - merged_owq_Koc10000.xlsx: summary table of VFSMOD results for Koc 100 L kg⁻¹
- comparison_vfsm424_with_deltaP_variantB_20250108.xlsx: calculation of ΔP with the mass balance approach; comparison of ΔP with 10th percentile ΔP from new CDFs (see Table 4)
- oldVFSMOD_CumAreaPercent_variantB.xlsx: Positions of old SWAN/VFSMOD scenarios (with old VFSMOD executable) on new CDFs (see Table 5)

Folder 7_Scripts

- Subfolder Mathematica contains the Mathematica script (Sav_GA_file2024_20250207.pdf) by Rafael Muñoz-Carpena to calculate the VFSSMOD parameter SAV (see section 2.2.2)
- Subfolder R_scripts contains the main R scripts used in this study, for reasons of transparency and comprehensible documentation. The R_scripts are the property of knoell Germany GmbH and licensed under GNU GENERAL PUBLIC LICENSE version 3.
 - recodeLUspade14.R (see section 6.7.2; Table A 14)
 - import_extended.R (this script performs several tasks; see sections 6.7.3 and 6.6)
 - createSpatialCDF.R (see section 6.7.4)
 - profileID_90th_PPerc.R (see section 6.7.5)
 - get_CumAreapercent_of_old_VFSSMOD.R (see section 2.4)
 - confusionMatrix.R (see sections 2.2.1, 6.10)
 - GPL-3.txt : license text

The scripts can be executed as is in R after setting the working directory to the path of folder 7_Scripts.